

The Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

*a non-profit
research institute affiliated with
the University of Bergen*

*Thormøhlensgate 47,
N-5006 Bergen
Norway*

NERSC Technical Report no. 393

NANSAT DOCUMENTATION

by

**Morten W. Hansen, Anton Korosov, Aleksander Vines,
Artem Moiseev, Jeong-Won Park**

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Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

Thormøhlensgate 47

N-5006 Bergen - NORWAY

Phone: +47 55 20 58 00 Fax: +47 55 20 58 01

E-mail: administrasjon@nersc.no

Web.site: <http://www.nersc.no>

*a non-profit environmental research center
affiliated with the university of Bergen*

REPORT

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SUMMARY Nansat is a scientist friendly Python toolbox for processing 2D satellite earth observation data. The main goal of Nansat is to facilitate: easy development and testing of scientific algorithms, easy analysis of geospatial data, and efficient operational processing.	
APPROVAL <i>Morten W. Hansen, author</i>	 Sebastian Mernild, Director

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Nansat is a scientist friendly Python toolbox for processing 2D satellite earth observation data.

The main **goal** of Nansat is to facilitate:

- easy development and testing of scientific algorithms,
- easy analysis of geospatial data, and
- efficient operational processing.

You can also find a detailed description of Nansat in our [paper](#) published in *Journal of Open Research Software* in 2016.

... and you can join the [mailing list](#).

1.1 Quickstart

The fastest way to install nansat:

- Install [Miniconda](#) on your platform of choice.
- When you install Miniconda on Windows, you will get a new app called “Anaconda Prompt”. Run this to access the conda installation.
- On Linux/OS X use a regular terminal and make sure PATH is set to contain the installation directory as explained by the installer.

```
conda create -n nansat -y Python=3.6
source activate nansat
# On windows you would need to omit source: *activate nansat*
conda install --yes -c conda-forge pythesint scipy=0.18.1 basemap gdal
pip install urllib3 pillow netcdf4 nansat
```

Nansat is now installed. For more details and other methods of installing Nansat, see below.

1.2 Requirements

Nansat requires the following packages:

- Python 2.7 or higher
- Numpy >=1.11.3
- GDAL >=2.2.3
- Pillow >=4.0.0
- netCDF4 >=1.3.1
- py-the-saurus-interface

- `cfunits`

The following packages are optional:

- `Scipy` 0.18.1
- Some mappers will not work without `scipy`. E.g. `sentinel1_ll`
- `Matplotlib` $\geq 2.1.1$
- `matplotlib` is required for Nansat methods `digitize_points()` and `crop_interactive()`
- `Basemap` $\geq 1.0.8$
- `basemap` is required in `write_domain_map()`

The most tricky to compile yourself is GDAL and Basemap. But one can find pre-built binaries available for different platforms. We recommend to install all dependencies with Conda, from the conda-forge channel. See instructions on this below.

1.3 Installing Requirements

You have three main options on how to install the requirements. These are described in the following three sections.

1.3.1 Install dependencies from Anaconda

This is the recommended approach for installing dependencies.

- Download `Miniconda` for your platform of choice.
- Install Miniconda
- When you install Miniconda on Windows, you will get a new app called “Anaconda Prompt”. Run this to access the conda installation.
- On Linux/OS X use a regular terminal and make sure `PATH` is set to contain the installation directory as explained by the installer.
- Run the following three commands:
 - `conda create -n nansat Python=3.6`
 - Or use Python version 3.5 or 2.7 if you need those versions.
 - `source activate nansat`
 - On windows you would omit ‘source’ and just run ‘`activate nansat`’
 - `conda install -yes -c conda-forge pythesint numpy scipy=0.18.1 matplotlib basemap netcdf4 gdal pillow urllib3`

1.3.2 Install Pre-built Binaries

One can find pre-built binaries available for different platforms. We do not have an overview over all the possible repositories where you can find binaries. But if you e.g. are on Ubuntu, the following procedure can be used to install dependencies with `apt` and `pip`.

```
sudo apt install virtualenv libgdall-dev python-dev python-gdal python-numpy python-
↳scipy \
python-matplotlib python-mpltoolkits.basemap python-requests
cd
virtualenv --no-site-packages nansat_env
source ~/nansat_env/bin/activate
export PYTHONPATH=/usr/lib/python2.7/dist-packages/
pip install pythesint pillow cfunits netcdf4 urllib3
```

1.3.3 Compile and Build Yourself

If you have the technical expertise to build all dependencies, and need to do it yourself, feel free to do so. If you need some aid, we would recommend you to look at how the corresponding [conda-forge feedstocks](#) have been built.

1.4 Installing Nansat

1.4.1 Install Nansat from source

If you want to install Nansat from source, you first need to install all requirements. Then proceed with one of the following methods

Install from git repository

git clone the master (most stable) or develop (cutting edge) branch, and install:

```
git clone https://github.com/nanscenter/nansat.git
checkout master (or develop, or a specific tag or branch)
python setup.py install
```

Nansat will then be added to your site-packages and can be used like any regular Python package.

Install with pip

Run the following command:

```
pip install nansat
```

Nansat will then be added to your site-packages and can be used like any regular Python package.

1.4.2 Special install for Nansat Developers

If you are working directly on the Nansat source, you need to install Nansat in the following way.

Git clone the develop branch (or another branch you are working on), and do:

```
python setup.py build_ext --inplace
```

The pixel functions C module is then compiled but no code is copied to site-packages and no linking is performed. Make sure to follow the [Nansat conventions](#) if you want to contribute to Nansat.

In addition to the regular dependencies, developers also need to install nose and mock. This can easily be done with *pip install nose mock*.

1.5 Use a self-provisioned Virtual Machine

Another option is to use a virtual machine managed by Virtualbox and provisioned using Vagrant and Ansible. We provide [configurations for virtual machines](#) for learning and development of Nansat. Following a clone of this repository and installation of virtualbox and vagrant, a vm used for courses can be installed by `vagrant up course`.

The package `nansat-lectures` contains several Jupyter notebooks with examples of how to use Nansat. Unfortunately, we have not been able to keep them fully updated. The most recently updated notebooks should, however, work.

2.1 Nansat: First Steps

2.1.1 Overview

The NANSAT package contains several classes:

- Nansat - open and read satellite data
- Domain - define grid for the region of interest
- Figure - create raster images (PNG, TIF)
- NSR - define spatial reference (SR)

2.1.2 Copy sample data

```
In [1]: import os
import shutil
import nansat
idir = os.path.join(os.path.dirname(nansat.__file__), 'tests', 'data/')
```

2.1.3 Open file with Nansat

```
In [2]: import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
%matplotlib inline
```

```
from nansat import Nansat
n = Nansat(idir+'gcps.tif')
```

2.1.4 Read information ABOUT the data (METADATA)

```
In [3]: print n
```

```
-----
/home/docs/checkouts/readthedocs.org/user_builds/nansat/conda/latest/lib/python2.7/site-packages/nansat
Mapper: genericBand : 1 L_645
  name: L_645
  dataType: 1
  standard_name: surface_upwelling_spectral_radiance_in_air_emerging_from_sea_water
  SourceFilename: /home/docs/checkouts/readthedocs.org/user_builds/nansat/conda/latest/lib/python2.7/
  time: 2011-08-15 10:05:00
  SourceBand: 1
  kv: surface_upwelling_spectral_radiance_in_air_emerging_from_sea_water
Band : 2 L_555
  name: L_555
  dataType: 1
  standard_name: surface_upwelling_spectral_radiance_in_air_emerging_from_sea_water
  SourceFilename: /home/docs/checkouts/readthedocs.org/user_builds/nansat/conda/latest/lib/python2.7/
  time: 2011-08-15 10:05:00
  SourceBand: 2
  kv: surface_upwelling_spectral_radiance_in_air_emerging_from_sea_water
Band : 3 L_469
  name: L_469
  dataType: 1
  standard_name: surface_upwelling_spectral_radiance_in_air_emerging_from_sea_water
  SourceFilename: /home/docs/checkouts/readthedocs.org/user_builds/nansat/conda/latest/lib/python2.7/
  time: 2011-08-15 10:05:00
  SourceBand: 3
  kv: surface_upwelling_spectral_radiance_in_air_emerging_from_sea_water
-----
Domain: [200 x 200]
-----
Projection:
GEOGCS["WGS 84",
  DATUM["WGS_1984",
    SPHEROID["WGS 84", 6378137, 298.257223563]],
  PRIMEM["Greenwich", 0],
  UNIT["degree", 0.0174532925199433]]
-----
Corners (lon, lat):
  ( 28.25,  71.54)  ( 30.87,  71.17)
  ( 27.14,  70.72)  ( 29.68,  70.35)
```

2.1.5 Read the actual DATA

```
In [4]: b1 = n[1]
```

2.1.6 Check what kind of data we have

```
In [5]: %whos
plt.imshow(b1);plt.colorbar()
```

```
plt.show()
```

Variable	Type	Data/Info
Nansat	type	<class 'nansat.nansat.Nansat'>
b1	ndarray	200x200: 40000 elems, type `uint8`, 40000 bytes
idir	str	/home/docs/checkouts/read<...>kages/nansat/tests/data/
n	Nansat	-----<...>0.72) (29.68, 70.35)\n
nansat	module	<module 'nansat' from '/h<...>ges/nansat/__init__.pyc'>
os	module	<module 'os' from '/home/<...>st/lib/python2.7/os.pyc'>
plt	module	<module 'matplotlib.pyplot<...>s/matplotlib/pyplot.pyc'>
shutil	module	<module 'shutil' from '/h<...>ib/python2.7/shutil.pyc'>

2.1.7 Find where the image is taken

```
In [6]: n.write_map('map.png', pltshow=True)
```

```
/home/docs/checkouts/readthedocs.org/user_builds/nansat/conda/latest/lib/python2.7/site-packages/nansat
warnings.warn(self.WRITE_MAP_WARNING, NansatFutureWarning)
```


3.1 nansat

3.1.1 nansat package

Submodules

nansat.domain module

class `nansat.domain.Domain` (*srs=None, ext=None, ds=None, lon=None, lat=None, name=""*,
logLevel=None)

Bases: `object`

Container for geographical reference of a raster

A Domain object describes all attributes of geographical reference of a raster:

- width and height (number of pixels)
- pixel size (e.g. in decimal degrees or in meters)
- relation between pixel/line coordinates and geographical coordinates (e.g. a linear relation)
- type of data projection (e.g. geographical or stereographic)

Parameters

- **srs** (*PROJ4 or EPSG or WKT or NSR or osr.SpatialReference()*) – Input parameter for `nansat.NSR()`
- **ext** (*string*) – some `gdalwarp` options + additional options [<http://www.gdal.org/gdalwarp.html>] Specifies extent, resolution / size Available options: (('te' or 'lle') and ('tr' or 'ts')) (e.g. 'lle -10 30 55 60 -ts 1000 1000' or 'te 100 2000 300 10000 -tr 300 200') -tr resolutionx resolutiony -ts sizex sizey -te xmin ymin xmax ymax -lle lonmin latmin lonmax latmax

- **ds** (*GDAL dataset*) –
- **lat** (*Numpy array*) – Grid with latitudes
- **lon** (*Numpy array*) – Grid with longitudes
- **name** (*string, optional*) – Name to be added to the Domain object
- **logLevel** (*int, optional*) – level of logging

Examples

```
>>> d = Domain(srs, ext) #size, extent and spatial reference is given by strings
>>> d = Domain(ds=GDALDataset) #size, extent copied from input GDAL dataset
>>> d = Domain(srs, ds=GDALDataset) # spatial reference is given by srs,
    but size and extent is determined from input GDAL dataset
>>> d = Domain(lon=lonGrid, lat=latGrid) # Size, extent and spatial reference is
    ↪given
    by two grids of longitude and latitude
```

Notes

The core of Domain is a GDAL Dataset. It has no bands, but only georeference information: rasterXsize, rasterYsize, GeoTransform and Projection or GCPs, etc. which fully describe dimensions and spatial reference of the grid.

There are three ways to store geo-reference in a GDAL dataset:

- Using GeoTransform to define linear relationship between raster pixel/line and geographical X/Y coordinates
- Using GCPs (set of Ground Control Points) to define non-linear relationship between pixel/line and X/Y
- Using Geolocation Array - full grids of X/Y coordinates for each pixel of a raster

The relation between X/Y coordinates of the raster and latitude/longitude coordinates is defined by projection type and projection parameters. These pieces of information are therefore stored in Domain:

- Type and parameters of projection + * GeoTransform, or * GCPs, or * GeolocationArrays

Domain has methods for basic operations with georeference information:

- creating georeference from input options;
- fetching corner, border or full grids of X/Y coordinates;
- making map of the georeferenced grid in a PNG or KML file;
- and some more...

The main attribute of Domain is a VRT object `self.vrt`. Nansat inherits from Domain and adds bands to `self.vrt`

Raises

- *NansatProjectionError* : occurs when *Projection()* is empty – despite it is required for creating *extentDic*.
- *OptionError* : occurs when the arguments are not proper.

See also:

Nansat.reproject() [<http://www.gdal.org/gdalwarp.html>] [<http://trac.osgeo.org/proj/>] [<http://spatialreference.org/>] [http://www.gdal.org/ogr/osr_tutorial.html]

KML_BASE = '<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>\n <kml xmlns="http://www.opengis.net'

OUTPUT_SEPARATOR = '-----\n'

REPROJECT_GCPs_WARNING = 'reproject_GCPs() will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use reprojec'

WRITE_MAP_WARNING = 'Domain.write_map() will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use nansat.wri'

azimuth_y (*reductionFactor=1*)

Calculate the angle of each pixel position vector with respect to the Y-axis (azimuth).

In general, azimuth is the angle from a reference vector (e.g., the direction to North) to the chosen position vector. The azimuth increases clockwise from direction to North. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Azimuth>

Parameters **reductionFactor** (*integer*) – factor by which the size of the output array is reduced

Returns **azimuth** – Values of azimuth in degrees in range 0 - 360

Return type numpy array

contains (*anotherDomain*)

Checks if this Domain fully covers another Domain

Returns **contains** – True if this Domain fully covers another Domain, False otherwise

Return type bool

get_border (*nPoints=10*)

Generate two vectors with values of lat/lon for the border of domain

Parameters **nPoints** (*int, optional*) – Number of points on each border

Returns **lonVec, latVec** – vectors with lon/lat values for each point at the border

Return type lists

get_border_geometry (**args, **kwargs*)

Get OGR Geometry of the border Polygon

Returns

Return type OGR Geometry, type Polygon

get_border_postgis ()

Get PostGIS formatted string of the border Polygon

Returns **str**

Return type 'PolygonFromText(PolygonWKT)'

get_border_wkt (**args, **kwargs*)

Creates string with WKT representation of the border polygon

Returns **WKTPolygon** – string with WKT representation of the border polygon

Return type string

get_corners ()

Get coordinates of corners of the Domain

Returns **lonVec, latVec** – vectors with lon/lat values for each corner

Return type lists

get_geolocation_grids (*stepSize=1*, *dstSRS=<sphinx.ext.autodoc.importer._MockObject object>*)

Get longitude and latitude grids representing the full data grid

If GEOLOCATION is not present in the self.vrt.dataset then grids are generated by converting pixel/line of each pixel into lat/lon If GEOLOCATION is present in the self.vrt.dataset then grids are read from the geolocation bands.

Parameters **stepSize** (*int*) – Reduction factor if output is desired on a reduced grid size

Returns

- **longitude** (*numpy array*) – grid with longitudes
- **latitude** (*numpy array*) – grid with latitudes

get_min_max_lon_lat ()

Get minimum and maximum of longitude and latitude geolocation grids

Returns **min_lon, max_lon, min_lat, max_lat**, – min/max lon/lat values for the Domain

Return type float

get_pixelsize_meters ()

Returns the pixelsize (deltaX, deltaY) of the domain

For projected domains, the exact result which is constant over the domain is returned. For geographic (lon-lat) projections, or domains with no geotransform, the haversine formula is used to calculate the pixel size in the center of the domain.

Returns **delta_x, delta_y** – pixel size in X and Y directions given in meters

Return type float

intersects (*anotherDomain*)

Checks if this Domain intersects another Domain

Returns **intersects** – True if Domains intersects, False otherwise

Return type bool

logger = None

name = None

overlaps (*anotherDomain*)

Checks if this Domain overlaps another Domain

Returns **overlaps** – True if Domains overlaps, False otherwise

Return type bool

reproject_GCPs (*srsString=""*)

reproject_gcps (*srs_string=""*)

Reproject all GCPs to a new spatial reference system

Necessary before warping an image if the given GCPs are in a coordinate system which has a singularity in (or near) the destination area (e.g. poles for lonlat GCPs)

Parameters **srs_string** (*string*) – SRS given as Proj4 string. If empty '+proj=stere' is used

Notes

Reprojects all GCPs to new SRS and updates GCPProjection

shape ()

Return Numpy-like shape of Domain object (ySize, xSize)

Returns **shape** – Numpy-like shape of Domain object (ySize, xSize)

Return type tuple of two INT

transform_points (*colVector, rowVector, DstToSrc=0, dstSRS=<sphinx.ext.autodoc.importer._MockObject object>*)

Transform given lists of X,Y coordinates into lon/lat or inverse

Parameters

- **colVector** (*lists*) – X and Y coordinates in pixel/line or lon/lat coordinate system
- **DstToSrc** (*0 or 1*) – 0 - forward transform (pix/line => lon/lat) 1 - inverse transformation
- **dstSRS** (*NSR*) – destination spatial reference

Returns **X, Y** – X and Y coordinates in lon/lat or pixel/line coordinate system

Return type lists

vrt = None

write_kml (*xmlFileName=None, kmlFileName=None*)

Write KML file with domains

Convert XML-file with domains into KML-file for GoogleEarth or write KML-file with the current Domain

Parameters

- **xmlFileName** (*string, optional*) – Name of the XML-file to convert. If only this value is given - kmlFileName=xmlFileName+'.kml'
- **kmlFileName** (*string, optional*) – Name of the KML-file to generate from the current Domain

write_kml_image (*kmlFileName, kmlFigureName=None*)

Create KML file for already projected image

Write Domain Image into KML-file for GoogleEarth

Parameters

- **kmlFileName** (*str*) – Name of the KML-file to generate from the current Domain
- **kmlFigureName** (*str*) – Name of the projected image stored in .png format

Examples

```
>>> n.undo(100) # cancel previous reprojection
>>> lons, lats = n.get_corners() # Get corners of the image and the pixel_
↳resolution
>>> srsString = '+proj=latlong +datum=WGS84 +ellps=WGS84 +no_defs'
>>> extentString = '-lle %f %f %f %f -ts 3000 3000'
    % (min(lons), min(lats), max(lons), max(lats))
>>> d = Domain(srs=srsString, ext=extentString) # Create Domain with
```

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```

    stereographic projection, corner coordinates and resolution 1000m
>>> n.reproject(d)
>>> n.write_figure(filename=figureName, bands=[3], clim=[0,0.15],
                  cmapName='gray', transparency=0)
>>> n.write_kml_image(kmlFileName=oPath + filename + '.kml',
                    kmlFigureName=figureName) # 6.

```

write_map (*outputFileName, lonVec=None, latVec=None, lonBorder=10.0, latBorder=10.0, figureSize=(6, 6), dpi=50, projection='cyl', resolution='c', continentsColor='coral', meridians=10, parallels=10, pColor='r', pLine='k', pAlpha=0.5, padding=0.0, merLabels=[False, False, False, False], parLabels=[False, False, False, False], pltshow=False, labels=None*)

Create an image with a map of the domain

nansat.exceptions module

exception nansat.exceptions.NansatGDALError

Bases: exceptions.Exception

Error from GDAL

exception nansat.exceptions.NansatGeolocationError

Bases: exceptions.Exception

Exception if geolocation is wrong (e.g., all lat/lon values are 0)

exception nansat.exceptions.NansatMissingProjectionError

Bases: exceptions.Exception

Exception raised if no (sub-) dataset has projection

exception nansat.exceptions.NansatProjectionError

Bases: exceptions.Exception

Cannot get the projection

exception nansat.exceptions.NansatReadError

Bases: exceptions.Exception

Exception if a file cannot be read with Nansat

exception nansat.exceptions.WrongMapperError

Bases: exceptions.Exception

Error for handling data that does not fit a given mapper

nansat.exporter module

class nansat.exporter.Exporter

Bases: object

Abstract class for export functions

DEFAULT_INSTITUTE = 'NERSC'

DEFAULT_SOURCE = 'satellite remote sensing'

EXPORT_ADD_GCPS_WARNING = 'Nansat.export(addGCPS=...) has no effect and will be disabled'

EXPORT_ADD_GEOLOC_WARNING = 'Nansat.export(addGeoloc=...) will be disabled from Nansat'

EXPORT_BOTTOMUP_WARNING = 'Nansat.export(bottomup=...) will be disabled from Nansat 1.
EXPORT_CREATED_WARNING = 'Nansat.export2thredds(createdTime=...) will be disabled from
EXPORT_FILENAME_WARNING = 'Nansat.export(fileName=...) will be disabled from Nansat 1.
EXPORT_MASKNAME_WARNING = 'Nansat.export2thredds(maskName=...) will be disabled from N
EXPORT_RM_METADATA_WARNING = 'Nansat.export(rmMetadata=...) will be disabled from Nans
UNWANTED_METADATA = ['dataType', 'SourceFilename', 'SourceBand', '_Unsigned', 'FillVal
export (*filename*=", *fileName*", *bands*=None, *rm_metadata*=None, *rmMetadata*=None, *addGeoloc*=None, *add_geolocation*=True, *addGCPs*=None, *driver*='netCDF', *bottomup*=None, *options*=None, *hardcopy*=False)
Export Nansat object into netCDF or GTiff file

Parameters

- **filename** (*str*) – output file name
- **bands** (*list* (*default*=None)) – Specify band numbers to export. If None, all bands are exported.
- **rm_metadata** (*list*) – metadata names for removal before export. e.g. ['name', 'colormap', 'source', 'sourceBands']
- **add_geolocation** (*bool*) – add geolocation array datasets to exported file?
- **driver** (*str*) – Name of GDAL driver (format)
- **bottomup** (*bool*) –
 - False: Write swath-projected data with rows and columns** organized as in the original product.
 - True:** Use the default behaviour of GDAL, which is to flip the rows
- **options** (*str* or *list*) – GDAL export options in format of: 'OPT=VAL', or ['OPT1=VAL1', 'OP2='VAL2'] See also http://www.gdal.org/frmt_netcdf.html
- **hardcopy** (*bool*) – Evaluate all bands just before export?
- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- **a netCDF file** (*Create*) –

Notes

If number of bands is more than one, serial numbers are added at the end of each band name. It is possible to fix it by changing line.4605 in GDAL/frmts/netcdf/netcdfdataset.cpp: 'if(nBands > 1) sprintf(szBandName,"%s%d",tmpMetadata,iBand);' → 'if(nBands > 1) sprintf(szBandName,"%s",tmpMetadata);'

CreateCopy fails in case the band name has special characters, e.g. the slash in 'HH/VV'.

Metadata strings with special characters are escaped with XML/HTML encoding.

Examples

```
# export all the bands into a netDCF 3 file >>> n.export(netcdf)
# export all bands into a GeoTiff >>> n.export(driver='GTiff')
export2thredds (filename, bands, metadata=None, mask_name=None, maskName=None,
                 rm_metadata=None, rmMetadata=None, time=None, created=None, creat-
                 edTime=None)
Export data into a netCDF formatted for THREDDS server
```

Parameters

- **filename** (*str*) – output file name
- **bands** (*dict*) –


```
{'band_name': {'type' ['>i1',] 'scale' : 0.1, 'offset' : 1000, 'metaKey1' : 'meta value
1', 'metaKey2' : 'meta value 2'}}
```

 dictionary sets parameters for band creation 'type' - string representation of data type in the output band 'scale' - sets scale_factor and applies scaling 'offset' - sets 'scale_offset' and applies offsetting other entries (e.g. 'units': 'K') set other metadata
- **metadata** (*dict*) – Global metadata to add
- **mask_name** (*str*) – if data include a mask band: give the mask name. Non-masked value is 64. if None: no mask is added
- **rm_metadata** (*list*) – unwanted metadata names which will be removed
- **time** (*list with datetime objects*) – acquisition time of original data. That value will be in time dim
- **created** (*datetime*) – date of creation. Will be in metadata 'created'

Note: Nansat object (self) has to be projected (with valid GeoTransform and valid Spatial reference information) but not with GCPs

Examples

```
# create THREDDS formatted netcdf file with all bands and time variable >>> n.export2thredds(filename)
# export only the first band and add global metadata >>> n.export2thredds(filename, ['L_469'], {'descrip-
tion': 'example'})
# export several bands and modify type, scale and offset >>> bands = {'L_645' : {'type': '>i2', 'scale':
0.1, 'offset': 0},
                             'L_555' : {'type': '>i2', 'scale': 0.1, 'offset': 0}}
```

```
>>> n.export2thredds(filename, bands)
```

nansat.figure module

```
class nansat.figure.Figure (nparray, **kwargs)
    Bases: object
```

Perform operations with graphical files: create, append legend, save.

Figure instance is created in the `Nansat.write_figure` method. The methods below are applied consequently in order to generate a figure from one or three bands, estimate min/max, apply logarithmic scaling, convert to uint8, append legend, save to a file

```

CAPTION_LOCATION_X = 0.1
CAPTION_LOCATION_Y = 0.25
CBAR_HEIGHT = 0.15
CBAR_HEIGHTMIN = 5
CBAR_LOCATION_X = 0.1
CBAR_LOCATION_Y = 0.5
CBAR_WIDTH = 0.8
CBTICK_LOC_ADJUST_X = 5
CBTICK_LOC_ADJUST_Y = 3
DEFAULT_EXTENSION = '.png'
LEGEND_HEIGHT = 0.1
TITLE_LOCATION_X = 0.1
TITLE_LOCATION_Y = 0.05

```

add_latlon_grids (***kwargs*)

Add lat/lon grid lines into the PIL image

Compute step of the grid. Make matrices with binarized lat/lon. Find edge (make line). Convert to mask. Add mask to PIL.

Parameters

- of `Figure__init__()` parameters (*Any*) –
- `latGrid` (*numpy array*) – array with values of latitudes
- `lonGrid` (*numpy array*) – array with values of longitudes
- `lonTicks` (*int or list*) – number of lines to draw or locations of gridlines
- `latTicks` (*int or list*) – number of lines to draw or locations of gridlines
- **Modifies** –
- -----
- `self.pilImg` –

add_latlon_labels (***kwargs*)

Add lat/lon labels along upper and left side

Compute step of labels. Get lat/lon for these labels from `latGrid`, `lonGrid`. Print labels to PIL in white

Parameters

- of `Figure__init__()` parameters (*Any*) –
- `latGrid` (*numpy array*) – array with values of latitudes
- `lonGrid` (*numpy array*) – array with values of longitudes
- `lonTicks` (*int or list*) – number of lines to draw or locations of gridlines

- **latTicks** (*int or list*) – number of lines to draw or locations of gridlines
- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- **self.pilImg** –

add_logo (***kwargs*)

Insert logo into the PIL image

Read logo from file as PIL Resize to the given size Pan using the given location Paste into pilImg

Parameters

- of **Figure.__init__()** parameters (*Any*) –
- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- **self.pilImg** –

apply_logarithm (***kwargs*)

Apply a tone curve to the array

After the normalization of the values from 0 to 1, logarithm is applied Then the values are converted to the normal scale.

Parameters

- of **Figure.__init__()** parameters (*Any*) –
- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- **self.array** (*numpy array*) –

apply_mask (***kwargs*)

Apply mask for coloring land, clouds, etc

If mask_array and mask_lut are provided as input parameters The pixels in self.array which have index equal to mask_lut key in mask_array will have color equal to mask_lut value

apply_mask should be called only after convert_palettesize (i.e. to uint8 data)

Parameters

- of **Figure.__init__()** parameters (*Any*) –
- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- **self.array** (*numpy array*) –

array = None

caption = ''

clim_from_histogram (***kwargs*)

Estimate min and max pixel values from histogram

if ratio=1.0, simply the minimum and maximum values are returned. if 0 < ratio < 1.0, get the histogram of the pixel values. Then get rid of (1.0-ratio)/2 from the both sides and return the minimum and maximum values.

Parameters of Figure.__init__() parameters (*Any*) –

Returns `clim` – minimum and maximum pixel values for each band

Return type numpy array 2D ((3x2) or (1x2))

clip (**kwargs)

Convert self.array to values between cmin and cmax

if pixel value < cmin, replaced to cmin. if pixel value > cmax, replaced to cmax.

Parameters

- of `Figure.__init__()` parameters (Any) –
- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- `self.array` (numpy array) –
- `self.cmax` (self.cmin,) –

`cmapName = 'jet'`

`cmax = [1.0]`

`cmin = [0.0]`

convert_palettesize (**kwargs)

Convert self.array to palette color size in uint8

Parameters

- of `Figure.__init__()` parameters (Any) –
- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- `self.array` (numpy array (=>uint8)) –

create_legend (**kwargs)

self.legend is replaced from None to PIL image

PIL image includes colorbar, caption, and titleString.

Parameters

- of `Figure.__init__()` parameters (Any) –
- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- `self.legend` (PIL image) –

create_pilImage (**kwargs)

self.create_pilImage is replaced from None to PIL image

If three images are given, create a image with RGB mode. if self.pilImgLegend is not None, it is pasted.

If one image is given, create a image with P(palette) mode. if self.pilImgLegend is not None, self.array is extended before create the pilImage and then paste pilImgLegend onto it.

Parameters

- of `Figure.__init__()` parameters (Any) –
- **Modifies** –

- -----
- **self.pilImg** (*PIL image*) – PIL image with / without the legend
- **self.array** (*replace to None*) –

```

extensionList = ['png', 'PNG', 'tif', 'TIF', 'bmp', 'BMP', 'jpg', 'JPG', 'jpeg', 'JPEG']
fontRatio = 1
fontSize = None
gamma = 2.0
latGrid = None
latTicks = 5
legend = False
logarithm = False
logoFileName = None
logoLocation = [0, 0]
logoSize = None
lonGrid = None
lonTicks = 5
mask_array = None
mask_lut = None
numOfColor = 250
numOfTicks = 5
palette = None
pilImg = None
pilImgLegend = None

```

process (***kwargs*)

Do all common operations for preparation of a figure for saving

1. Modify default values of parameters by the provided ones (if any)
2. Clip to min/max
3. Apply logarithm if required
4. Convert data to uint8
5. Create palette
6. Apply mask for colouring land, clouds, etc if required
7. Create legend if required
8. Create PIL image
9. Add logo if required

Parameters

- of **Figure.__init__()** parameters (*Any*) –

- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- **self.d** –
- **self.array** –
- **self.palette** –
- **self.pilImgLegend** –
- **self.pilImg** –

ratio = 1.0

save (*fileName*, ***kwargs*)

Save self.pilImg to a physical file

If given extension is JPG, convert the image mode from Palette to RGB

Parameters

- **fileName** (*string*) – name of outputfile
- of **Figure.__init__()** **parameters** (*Any*) –
- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- **self.pilImg** (*None*) –

subsetArraySize = 100000

titleString = ''

transparency = None

nansat.geolocation module

class nansat.geolocation.**Geolocation** (*x_vrt*, *y_vrt*, ***kwargs*)

Bases: object

Container for GEOLOCATION data

Keeps references to bands with X and Y coordinates, offset and step of pixel and line. All information is stored in dictionary self.data

Instance of Geolocation is used in VRT and ususalY created in a Mapper.

data = None

classmethod **from_dataset** (*dataset*)

Create geolocation from GDAL dataset :param dataset: input dataset to copy Geolocation metadata from :type dataset: gdal.Dataset

classmethod **from_filenames** (*x_filename*, *y_filename*, ***kwargs*)

Create geolocation from names of files with geolocation :param x_filename: name of file for X-dataset :type x_filename: str :param y_filename: name of file for Y-dataset :type y_filename: str :param ***kwargs*: parameters for self._init_data() :type ***kwargs*: dict

get_geolocation_grids ()

Read values of geolocation grids

x_vrt = None

`y_vrt = None`

nansat.nansat module

class `nansat.nansat.Nansat` (`filename=""`, `fileName=""`, `mapper=""`, `mapperName=""`, `domain=None`, `array=None`, `parameters=None`, `log_level=30`, `logLevel=None`, `**kwargs`)

Bases: `nansat.domain.Domain`, `nansat.exporter.Exporter`

Container for geospatial data. Performs all high-level operations.

`n = Nansat(filename)` opens the file with satellite or model data for reading, adds scientific metadata to bands, and prepares the data for further handling.

Parameters

- **filename** (*str*) – uri of the input file or OpeNDAP datastream
- **mapper** (*str*) – name of the mapper from `nansat/mappers` dir. E.g. 'sentinel1_l1', 'asar', 'hirlam', 'meris_l1', 'meris_l2', etc.
- **log_level** (*int*) – Level of logging. See: <http://docs.python.org/howto/logging.html>
- **kwargs** (*additional arguments for mappers*) –

Examples

```
>>> n1 = Nansat(filename)
>>> n2 = Nansat(sentinel1_filename, mapper='sentinel1_l1')
>>> array1 = n1[1]
>>> array2 = n2['sigma0_HV']
```

Notes

The instance of `Nansat` class (the object `<n>`) contains information about geographical reference of the data (e.g raster size, pixel resolution, type of projection, etc) and about bands with values of geophysical variables (e.g. water leaving radiance, normalized radar cross section, chlorophyll concentraion, etc). The object `<n>` has methods for high-level operations with data. E.g.: * reading data from file (`Nansat.__getitem__`); * visualization (`Nansat.write_figure`); * changing geographical reference (`Nansat.reproject`); * exporting (`Nansat.export`) * and much more...

`Nansat` inherits from `Domain` (container of geo-reference information) `Nansat` uses instance of `VRT` (wrapper around GDAL VRT-files) `Nansat` uses instance of `Figure` (collection of methods for visualization)

ALT_FILL_VALUE = -10000.0

FILL_VALUE = 9.96921e+36

INIT_BANDID_WARNING = 'Nansat.method(bandID=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use Nansat.f

INIT_DOMAIN_WARNING = 'Nansat(domain=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use Nansat.f

INIT_DSTDOMAIN_WARNING = 'Nansat.method(dstDomain=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1.

INIT_FILENAME_WARNING = 'Nansat(fileName=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use Nansat.f

INIT_GETBANDNUMBER_WARNING = 'Nansat._get_band_number() will be disabled in Nansat 1.1

INIT_LOG_WARNING = 'Nansat(logLevel=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use Nansat(lo

`INIT_MAPPER_WARNING = 'Nansat (mapperName=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use Nansat`

`INIT_RESAMPLEALG_WARNING = 'Nansat.method(eResampleAlg=...) will be disabled in Nansat`

`add_band (array, parameters=None, nomem=False)`

Add band from numpy array with metadata.

Create VRT object which contains VRT and RAW binary file and append it to `self.vrt.band_vrts`

Parameters

- **array** (*ndarray*) – new band data. Shape should be equal to shape
- **parameters** (*dict*) – band metadata: wkv, name, etc. (or for several bands)
- **nomem** (*bool*) – saves the vrt to a tempfile on disk?

Notes

Creates VRT object with VRT-file and RAW-file. Adds band to the `self.vrt`.

Examples

```
>>> n.add_band(array, {'name': 'new_data'}) # add new band and metadata, keep_
↳ in memory
>>> n.add_band(array, nomem=True) # add new band, keep on disk
```

`add_bands (arrays, parameters=None, nomem=False)`

Add bands from numpy arrays with metadata.

Create VRT object which contains VRT and RAW binary file and append it to `self.vrt.band_vrts`

Parameters

- **arrays** (*list of ndarrays*) – new band data. Shape should be equal to shape
- **parameters** (*list of dict*) – band metadata: wkv, name, etc. (or for several bands)
- **nomem** (*bool*) – saves the vrt to a tempfile on disk?

Notes

Creates VRT object with VRT-file and RAW-file. Adds band to the `self.vrt`.

Examples

```
>>> n.add_bands([array1, array2]) # add new bands, keep in memory
```

`bands ()`

Make a dictionary with all metadata from all bands

Returns **b** – key = N, value = dict with all band metadata

Return type dictionary

crop (*x_offset, y_offset, x_size, y_size, allow_larger=False*)

Crop Nansat object

Create superVRT, modify the Source Rectangle (SrcRect) and Destination Rectangle (DstRect) tags in the VRT file for each band in order to take only part of the original image, create new GCPs or new GeoTransform for the cropped object.

Parameters

- **x_offset** (*int*) – pixel offset of subimage
- **y_offset** (*int*) – line offset of subimage
- **x_size** (*int*) – width in pixels of subimage
- **y_size** (*int*) – height in pixels of subimage
- **allow_larger** (*bool*) – Allow resulting extent to be larger than the original image?

Notes

`self.vrt` : super-VRT is created with modified SrcRect and DstRect

Returns extent – `x_offset` - X offset in the original dataset `y_offset` - Y offset in the original dataset `x_size` - width of the new dataset `y_size` - height of the new dataset

Return type (`x_offset, y_offset, x_size, y_size`)

Examples

```
>>> extent = n.crop(10, 20, 100, 200)
```

crop_interactive (*band=1, maxwidth=1000, **kwargs*)

Interactively select boundary and crop Nansat object

Parameters

- **band** (*int or str*) – id of the band to show for interactive selection of boundaries
- **maxwidth** (*int*) – large input data is downsampled to `<maxwidth>`
- ****kwargs** (*keyword arguments for imshow*) –

Notes

`self.vrt` [VRT] superVRT is created with modified SrcRect and DstRect

Returns extent – `x_offset` - X offset in the original dataset `y_offset` - Y offset in the original dataset `x_size` - width of the new dataset `y_size` - height of the new dataset

Return type (`x_offset, y_offset, x_size, y_size`)

Examples

```
>>> extent = n.crop_interactive(band=1) # crop a subimage interactively
```

crop_lonlat (*lonlim, latlim*)

Crop Nansat object to fit into given longitude/latitude limit

Parameters

- **lonlim** (*list of 2 float*) – min/max of longitude
- **latlim** (*list of 2 float*) – min/max of latitude

Notes

self.vrt [VRT] crops vrt to size that corresponds to lon/lat limits

Returns extent – x_offset - X offset in the original dataset y_offset - Y offset in the original dataset x_size - width of the new dataset y_size - height of the new dataset

Return type (x_offset, y_offset, x_size, y_size)

Examples

```
>>> extent = n.crop(lonlim=[-10,10], latlim=[-20,20]) # crop for given lon/
↳lat limits
```

digitize_points (*band=1, **kwargs*)

Get coordinates of interactively digitized points

Parameters

- **band** (*int or str*) – ID of Nansat band
- ****kwargs** (*keyword arguments for imshow*) –

Returns points – list of 2xN arrays of points to be used in Nansat.get_transect()

Return type list

extend (*left=0, right=0, top=0, bottom=0*)

Extend domain from four sides

Parameters

- **left** (*int*) – number of pixels to add from left side
- **right** (*int*) – number of pixels to add from right side
- **top** (*int*) – number of pixels to add from top side
- **bottom** (*int*) – number of pixels to add from bottom side

Notes

Changes self.vrt by adding negative offset or setting size to be large that original size.

fileName

filename = None

classmethod from_domain (*domain, array=None, parameters=None, log_level=30*)

Create Nansat object from input Domain [and array with data]

Parameters

- **domain** (*Domain*) – Defines spatial reference system and geographical extent.
- **array** (*numpy NDarray*) – Data for the first band. Shape must correspond to shape of <domain>
- **parameters** (*dict*) – Metadata for the first band. May contain 'name', 'wkv' and other keys.
- **log_level** (*int*) – Level of logging.

get_GDALRasterBand (*band_id=1, bandID=None*)

Get a GDALRasterBand of a given Nansat object

If str is given find corresponding band number If int is given check if band with this number exists. Get a GDALRasterBand from vrt.

Parameters **band_id** (*int or str*) – if int - a band number of the band to fetch if str
band_id = {'name': band_id}

Returns**Return type** GDAL RasterBand**Example**

```
>>> b = n.get_GDALRasterBand(1)
>>> b = n.get_GDALRasterBand('sigma0')
```

get_band_number (*band_id*)

Return absolute band number

Check if given band_id is valid Return absolute number of the band in the VRT

Parameters **band_id** (*int or str or dict*) – if int : checks if such band exists and returns band_id if str : finds band with corresponding name if dict : finds first band with given metadata

Returns int**Return type** absolute band number**get_metadata** (*key=None, band_id=None, bandID=None*)

Get metadata from self.vrt.dataset

Parameters

- **key** (*string, optional*) – name of the metadata key. If not given all metadata is returned
- **band_id** (*int or str, optional*) – number or name of band to get metadata from. If not given, global metadata is returned

Returns

- * *string with metadata if key is given and found*
- * *empty string if key is given and not found*
- * *dictionary with all metadata if key is not given*

get_transect (*points, bands, lonlat=True, smooth_radius=0, smooth_function=<sphinx.ext.autodoc.importer._MockObject object>, data=None, cornersonly=False*)

Get values from transect from given vector of points

Parameters

- **points** (*2xN list or array, N (number of points) >= 1*) – coordinates [[x1, x2, y2], [y1, y2, y3]]
- **bands** (*list of int or string*) – elements of the list are band number or band Name
- **lonlat** (*bool*) – If the points in lat/lon, then True. If the points in pixel/line, then False.
- **smooth_radius** (*int*) – If smoothRadius is greater than 0, smooth every transect pixel as the median or mean value in a circle with radius equal to the given number.
- **smooth_function** (*func*) – function for averaging values collected within smooth radius
- **data** (*ndarray*) – alternative array with data to take values from

Returns transect

Return type numpy record array

has_band (*band*)

Check if self has band with name <band> :param band: name or standard_name of the band to check :type band: str

Returns

Return type True/False if band exists or not

list_bands (*do_print=True*)

Show band information of the given Nansat object

Show serial number, longName, name and all parameters for each band in the metadata of the given Nansat object.

Parameters do_print (*boolean*) – print on screen?

Returns outString – formatted string with bands info

Return type String

logger = None

mapper = None

name = None

path = None

reproject (*dst_domain=None, dstDomain=None, resample_alg=0, eResampleAlg=None, block_size=None, tps=None, skip_gcps=1, addmask=True, **kwargs*)

Change projection of the object based on the given Domain

Create superVRT from self.vrt with AutoCreateWarpedVRT() using projection from the dst_domain. Modify XML content of the warped vrt using the Domain parameters. Generate warpedVRT and replace self.vrt with warpedVRT. If current object spans from 0 to 360 and dst_domain is west of 0, the object is shifted by 180 westwards.

Parameters

- **dst_domain** (*domain*) – destination Domain where projection and resolution are set

- **resample_alg** (*int* (*GDALResampleAlg*)) – 0 : NearestNeighbour 1 : Bilinear 2 : Cubic, 3 : CubicSpline 4 : Lancos
- **block_size** (*int*) – size of blocks for resampling. Large value decrease speed but increase accuracy at the edge
- **tps** (*bool*) – Apply Thin Spline Transformation if source or destination has GCPs Usage of TPS can also be triggered by setting `self.vrt.tps=True` before calling to reproject. This options has priority over `self.vrt.tps`
- **skip_gcps** (*int*) – Using TPS can be very slow if the number of GCPs are large. If this parameter is given, only every [skip_gcp] GCP is used, improving calculation time at the cost of accuracy. If not given explicitly, 'skip_gcps' is fetched from the metadata of self, or from `dst_domain` (as set by mapper or user). [defaults to 1 if not specified, i.e. using all GCPs]
- **addmask** (*bool*) – If True, add band 'swathmask'. 1 - valid data, 0 no-data. This band is used to replace no-data values with `np.nan`

Notes

`self.vrt` : VRT object with dataset replaced to warpedVRT dataset Integer data is returned by integer. Round off to decimal place. If you do not want to round off, convert the data types to `GDT_Float32`, `GDT_Float64`, or `GDT_CFloat32`.

See also:

`http()` //www.gdal.org/gdalwarp.html

resize (*factor=None, width=None, height=None, pixelsize=None, resample_alg=-1, eResampleAlg=None*)
Proportional resize of the dataset.

The dataset is resized as (`x_size*factor`, `y_size*factor`) If desired width, height or pixelsize is specified, the scaling factor is calculated accordingly. If GCPs are given in a dataset, they are also rewritten.

Parameters

- **factor** (*float, optional, default=1*) – Scaling factor for width and height > 1 means increasing domain size < 1 means decreasing domain size
- **width** (*int, optional*) – Desired new width in pixels
- **height** (*int, optional*) – Desired new height in pixels
- **pixelsize** (*float, optional*) – Desired new pixelsize in meters (approximate). A factor is calculated from ratio of the current pixelsize to the desired pixelsize.
- **resample_alg** (*int* (*GDALResampleAlg*), *optional*) –
-1 [Average (default),] 0 : NearestNeighbour 1 : Bilinear, 2 : Cubic, 3 : CubicSpline, 4 : Lancos

Notes

`self.vrt.dataset` [VRT dataset of VRT object] raster size are modified to downscaled size. If GCPs are given in the dataset, they are also overwritten.

set_metadata (*key=""*, *value=""*, *band_id=None*, *bandID=None*)

Set metadata to self.vrt.dataset

Parameters

- **key** (*string* or *dictionary with strings*) – name of the metadata, or dictionary with metadata names, values
- **value** (*string*) – value of metadata
- **band_id** (*int* or *str*) – number or name of band Without : global metadata is set

Notes

self.vrt.dataset : sets metadata in GDAL current dataset

time_coverage_end

time_coverage_start

undo (*steps=1*)

Undo reproject, resize, add_band or crop of Nansat object

Restore the self.vrt from self.vrt.vrt

Parameters **steps** (*int*) – How many steps back to undo

Notes

Modifies self.vrt

vrt = None

watermask (*mod44path=None*, *dst_domain=None*, *dstDomain=None*, ***kwargs*)

Create numpy array with watermask (water=1, land=0)

250 meters resolution watermask from MODIS 44W Product: <http://www.glcfc.umd.edu/data/watermask/>

Watermask is stored as tiles in TIF(LZW) format and a VRT file All files are stored in one directory. A tarball with compressed TIF and VRT files should be additionally downloaded from the Nansat documentation page: <http://nansat.readthedocs.io/en/latest/source/features.html#differentiating-between-land-and-water>

The method : Gets the directory either from input parameter or from environment variable MOD44WPATH Open Nansat object from the VRT file Reprojects the watermask onto the current object using reproject() or reproject_on_jcps() Returns the reprojected Nansat object

Parameters

- **mod44path** (*string*) – path with MOD44W Products and a VRT file
- **dst_domain** (*Domain*) – destination domain other than self
- **tps** (*Bool*) – Use Thin Spline Transformation in reprojection of watermask? See also Nansat.reproject()
- **skip_gcps** (*int*) – Factor to reduce the number of GCPs by and increase speed See also Nansat.reproject()

Returns watermask

Return type Nansat object with water mask in current projection

See also:

`http()` //www.glcf.umd.edu/data/watermask/

`http()` //nansat.readthedocs.io/en/latest/source/features.html#differentiating-between-land-and-water

`write_figure` (*filename=""*, *bands=1*, *clim=None*, *addDate=False*, *array_modfunc=None*, *filename=""*, ***kwargs*)

Save a raster band to a figure in graphical format.

Get numpy array from the band(s) and band information specified either by given band number or band id. – If three bands are given, merge them and create PIL image. – If one band is given, create indexed image. Create Figure object and: Adjust the array brightness and contrast using the given min/max or histogram. Apply logarithmic scaling of color tone. Generate and append legend. Save the PIL output image in PNG or any other graphical format. If the filename extension is ‘tif’, the figure file is converted to GeoTiff

Parameters

- **filename** (*str*) – Output file name. if one of extensions ‘png’, ‘PNG’, ‘tif’, ‘TIF’, ‘bmp’, ‘BMP’, ‘jpg’, ‘JPG’, ‘jpeg’, ‘JPEG’ is included, specified file is created. otherwise, ‘png’ file is created.
- **bands** (*integer or string or list (elements are integer or string),*) – default = 1 the size of the list has to be 1 or 3. if the size is 3, RGB image is created based on the three bands. Then the first element is Red, the second is Green, and the third is Blue.
- **clim** (*list with two elements or 'hist' to specify range of colormap*) – None (default) : min/max values are fetched from WKV, fallback-‘hist’ [min, max] : min and max are numbers, or [[min, min, min], [max, max, max]]: three bands used ‘hist’ : a histogram is used to calculate min and max values
- **addDate** (*boolean*) – False (default) : no date will be added to the caption True : the first time of the object will be added to the caption
- **array_modfunc** (*None*) – None (default) : figure created using array in provided band function : figure created using array modified by provided function
- ****kwargs** (*parameters for Figure()*) –

Notes

if filename is specified, creates image file

Returns

Return type Figure object

Example

```
>>> n.write_figure('test.jpg') # write indexed image
>>> n.write_figure('test_rgb_hist.jpg', clim='hist', bands=[1, 2, 3]) # RGB_
↪ image
>>> n.write_figure('r09_log3_leg.jpg', logarithm=True, legend=True,
                    gamma=3, titleString='Title', fontSize=30,
                    numOfTicks=15) # add legend
>>> n.write_figure(filename='transparent.png', bands=[3],
```

(continues on next page)

(continued from previous page)

```
mask_array=wmArray,
mask_lut={0: [0,0,0]},
clim=[0,0.15], cmapName='gray',
transparency=[0,0,0]) # write transparent image
```

See also:

Figure()

http() //www.scipy.org/Cookbook/Matplotlib/Show_colormaps**write_geotiffimage** (*filename*, *band_id=1*, *bandID=None*)

Writes an 8-bit GeoTiff image for a given band.

The colormap is fetched from the metadata item 'colormap'. Fallback colormap is 'gray'.

Color limits are fetched from the metadata item 'minmax'. If 'minmax' is not specified, min and max of the raster data is used.

The method can be replaced by using `nansat.write_figure()`. However, `write_figure` uses PIL, which does not allow Tiff compression. This gives much larger files.**Parameters**

- **filename** (*str*) –
- **band_id** (*int or str*) –

nansat.node module**class** `nansat.node.Node` (*tag*, *value=None*, ***attributes*)Bases: `object`

Rapidly assemble XML using minimal coding.

By Bruce Eckel, (c)2006 MindView Inc. www.MindView.net Permission is granted to use or modify without payment as long as this copyright notice is retained.

Everything is a Node, and each Node can either have a value or subnodes. Subnodes can be appended to Nodes using '+=', and a group of Nodes can be strung together using '+'.

Create a node containing a value by saying `Node('tag', 'value')` You can also give attributes to the node in the constructor: `Node('tag', 'value', attr1 = 'attr1', attr2 = 'attr2')` or without a value: `Node('tag', attr1 = 'attr1', attr2 = 'attr2')`To produce xml from a finished Node `n`, say `n.xml()` (for nicely formatted output) or `n.rawxml()`.You can read and modify the attributes of an xml Node using `getAttribute()`, `setAttribute()`, or `delAttribute()`.You can find the value of the first subnode with `tag == 'tag'` by saying `n['tag']`. If there are multiple instances of `n['tag']`, this will only find the first one, so you should use `node()` or `nodeList()` to narrow your search down to a Node that only has one instance of `n['tag']` first.You can replace the value of the first subnode with `tag == 'tag'` by saying `n['tag'] = newValue`. The same issues exist as noted in the above paragraph.You can find the first node with `tag == 'tag'` by saying `node('tag')`. If there are multiple nodes with the same tag at the same level, use `nodeList('tag')`.

The Node class is also designed to create a kind of 'domain specific language' by subclassing Node to create Node types specific to your problem domain.

This implementation uses `xml.dom.minidom` which is available in the standard Python 2.4 library. However, it can be retargeted to use other XML libraries without much effort.

static create (*dom*)

Create a Node representation, given either a string representation of an XML doc, or a dom.

delAttribute (*name*)

Remove XML attribute with this name.

delNode (*tag, options=None*)

Recursively find nodes containing subnodes with this tag and remove subnodes

options [dictionary] if there are several tags, specify a node by their attributes.

doc = `<xml.dom.minidom.Document instance>`

dom ()

Lazily create a minidom from the information stored in this Node object.

find_dom_child (*dom, tagName, n=0*)

Recursively find child of the dom

getAttribute (*name*)

Read XML attribute of this node.

getAttributeList ()

get attributes and value from the node and return their lists

insert (*contents*)

return Node of the node with inserted `<contents>`

node (*tag, elemNum=0*)

Recursively find the first subnode with this tag.

elemNum [int] if there are several same tag, specify which element to take.

nodeList (*tag*)

Produce a list of subnodes with the same tag. Note: It only makes sense to do this for the immediate children of a node. If you went another level down, the results would be ambiguous, so the user must choose the node to iterate over.

rawxml ()

replaceAttribute (*name, value*)

replace XML attribute of this node.

replaceNode (*tag, elemNum=0, newNode=None*)

Find the first subnode with this tag and replace with given node.

tag [str] node tag

elemNum [int] number of subnode among other subnodes with similar tag

replaceTag (*oldTag, newTag*)

Replace tag name

setAttribute (*name, item*)

Modify XML attribute of this node.

tagList ()

Produce a list of all tags of the immediate children

xml (*separator='u' '*)

nansat.nsr module

nansat.pointbrowser module

class `nansat.pointbrowser.PointBrowser` (*data*, *fmt*='x-k', *force_interactive*=True, ***kwargs*)
Click on raster images shown by `plt.imshow` and get the X-Y coordinates.

Parameters

- **data** (*ndarray*) – image to `imshow`
- **transect** (*bool*) – if True, get transects / points if False, get only points
- **force_interactive** (*bool*) – force PointBrowser to interactive mode? (True for regular use, False for tests)
- ****kwargs** (*dict*) – optional parameters for `imshow`

Note: `self.fig` : pyplot Figure `self.data` : *ndarray* with data `self.ax` : axes `self.points` : plot with points `self.line` : plot with points `self.coordinates`: container for recorded coordinates

ax = None

coordinates = None

data = None

fig = None

fmt = None

get_points ()

Enables the onclick events and returns the points.

The format of the returned array: `[array([[x1,...,xn],[y1,...,yn]]),array([[xn+1,...],[yn+1,...]]),...]` Each 'array' element is a `numpy.ndarray` and represents one transect, where `x1,y1` is the first point in the first transect, and `xn,yn` the last point in the first transect. The inner x/y-arrays are also `numpy.ndarray`s

lines = None

onclick (*event*)

Process mouse onclick event Append coordinates of the click to `self.coordinates`, add point and 2D line to `self.points` If click is outside, nothing is done If click with 'z' pressed, nothing is done If click with 'anykey', new line is started

Parameters *event* (`matplotlib.mouse_event`) –

points = None

text_ax = None

nansat.tools module

exception `nansat.tools.GDALError` (**args*, ***kwargs*)

Bases: `exceptions.Exception`

exception `nansat.tools.GeolocationError` (**args*, ***kwargs*)

Bases: `exceptions.Exception`

exception `nansat.tools.NansatReadError` (**args*, ***kwargs*)

Bases: `exceptions.Exception`

exception `nansat.tools.OptionError(*args, **kwargs)`

Bases: `exceptions.Exception`

exception `nansat.tools.ProjectionError(*args, **kwargs)`

Bases: `exceptions.Exception`

exception `nansat.tools.WrongMapperError(*args, **kwargs)`

Bases: `exceptions.Exception`

`nansat.tools.add_logger(logName="", logLevel=None)`

Creates and returns logger with default formatting for Nansat

Parameters `logName` (*string, optional*) – Name of the logger

Returns

Return type `logging.logger`

See also:

http() [//docs.python.org/howto/logging.html](http://docs.python.org/howto/logging.html)

`nansat.tools.get_random_color(c0=None, minDist=100, low=0, high=255)`

Create random color which is far enough from the input color

Parameters

- **c0** (*str*) – hexademical representation of the color (e.g. `'#ff0000'` for red)
- **minDist** (*int*) – minimal distance to input color

Returns `c0` – hexademical representation of the new random color

Return type `str`

`nansat.tools.haversine(lon1, lat1, lon2, lat2)`

Calculate the great circle distance between two points on the spherical earth (specified in decimal degrees)

`nansat.tools.initial_bearing(lon1, lat1, lon2, lat2)`

Initial bearing when traversing from point1 (lon1, lat1) to point2 (lon2, lat2)

See <http://www.movable-type.co.uk/scripts/latlong.html>

Parameters

- **lat1** (*lon1,*) – longitude and latitude of start point
- **lat2** (*lon2,*) – longitude and latitude of end point

Returns `initial_bearing` – The initial bearing (azimuth direction) when heading out from the start point towards the end point along a great circle.

Return type `float`

`nansat.tools.parse_time(time_string)`

Parse time string accounting for possible wrong formatting :param time_string: string with date and time :type time_string: str

Returns `time_value`

Return type `datetime object`

`nansat.tools.register_colormaps()`

Create custom colormaps and register them

`nansat.tools.remove_keys(dict, keys)`

`nansat.tools.test_openable` (*fname*)

`nansat.tools.write_domain_map` (*border*, *out_filename*, *lon_vec=None*, *lat_vec=None*,
lon_border=10.0, *lat_border=10.0*, *figure_size=(6, 6)*, *dpi=50*,
projection='cyl', *resolution='c'*, *continets_color='coral'*, *meridians=10*,
parallels=10, *p_color='r'*, *p_line='k'*, *p_alpha=0.5*,
padding=0.0, *mer_labels=[False, False, False, False]*,
par_labels=[False, False, False, False], *pltshow=False*, *labels=None*)

Create an image with a map of the domain

Uses Basemap to create a World Map Adds a semitransparent patch with outline of the Domain Writes to an image file

Parameters

- **out_filename** (*string*) – name of the output file name
- **lon_vec** (*[floats]* or *[[floats]]*) – longitudes of patches to display
- **lat_vec** (*[floats]* or *[[floats]]*) – latitudes of patches to display
- **lon_border** (*float*) – 10, horizontal border around patch (degrees of longitude)
- **lat_border** (*float*) – 10, vertical border around patch (degrees of latitude)
- **figure_size** (*tuple of two integers*) – (6, 6), size of the generated figure in inches
- **dpi** (*int*) – 50, resolution of the output figure (size 6,6 and dpi 50 produces 300 x 300 figure)
- **projection** (*string, one of Basemap projections*) – ‘cyl’, projection of the map
- **resolution** (*string, resolution of the map*) – ‘c’, crude ‘l’, low ‘i’, intermediate ‘h’, high ‘f’, full
- **continets_color** (*string or any matplotlib color representation*) – ‘coral’, color of continets
- **meridians** (*int*) – 10, number of meridians to draw
- **parallels** (*int*) – 10, number of parallels to draw
- **p_color** (*string or any matplotlib color representation*) – ‘r’, color of the Domain patch
- **p_line** (*string or any matplotlib color representation*) – ‘k’, color of the Domain outline
- **p_alpha** (*float 0 - 1*) – 0.5, transparency of Domain patch
- **padding** (*float*) – 0., width of white padding around the map
- **mer_labels** (*list of 4 booleans*) – where to put meridian labels, see also `Basemap.drawmeridians()`
- **par_labels** (*list of 4 booleans*) – where to put parallel labels, see also `Basemap.drawparallels()`
- **labels** (*list of str*) – labels to print on top of patches

nansat.vrt module

class nansat.vrt.VRT (*x_size=1, y_size=1, metadata=None, nomem=False, **kwargs*)

Bases: object

Wrapper around GDAL VRT-file

The GDAL VRT-file is an XML-file. It contains all metadata, geo-reference information and information ABOUT each band including band metadata, reference to the bands in the source file. VRT-class performs all operation on VRT-files: create, copy, modify, read, write, add band, add GeoTransform, set Projection, etc. It uses either GDAL methods for these operations (e.g. Create, AddBand, SetMetadata, AutoCreateWarpedVRT, etc.) or reads/writes the XML-file directly (e.g. remove_geotransform, get_warped_vrt, etc).

The core of the VRT object is GDAL dataset <self.dataset> generated by the GDAL VRT-Driver. The respective VRT-file is located in /vismem and has a random name.

GDAL data model doesn't have place for geolocaion arrays therefore VRT-object has instance of Geolocation (self.geolocation) an object to keep information about Geolocation metadata: reference to file with source data, pixel and line step and offset, etc.

Domain has an instance of VRT-class <self.vrt>. It keeps only geo- reference information.

All Mappers inherit from VRT. When Nansat opens a file it loops through list of mappers, selects the one appropriate for the input file, and creates an instance of Mapper.

Nansat has one instances of Mapper-class (>=VRT-class): self.vrt. It holds VRT-file in original projection (derived from the input file). After most of the operations with Nansat object (e.g. reproject, crop, resize, add_band) self.vrt is replaced with a new VRT object which has reference to the previous VRT object inside (self.vrt.vrt).

Parameters

- **x_size** (*int*) – width of self.dataset
- **y_size** (*int*) – arguments for VRT()
- **metadata** (*dict*) – dictionray with metadata keys (str) and values (str)
- **nomem** (*bool*) – don't create VRT in VSI memory?

Notes

adds self.logger, self.driver, self.filename, self.band_vrts, self.tps, self.vrt adds self.dataset - GDAL Dataset without bands and with size=(x_zie, y_size) adds metadata to self.dataset writes VRT file content to self.filename

COMPLEX_SOURCE_XML = <string.Template object>

INIT_ARRAY_WARNING = u'VRT(array=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use VRT.from_arr

INIT_DATASETPARAMS_WARNING = u'VRT(srcGeoTransform, srcProjection, srcRasterXSize, src

INIT_GDALDATASET_WARNING = u'VRT(gdalDataset=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use V

INIT_GEOLOCATIONARRAY_WARNING = u'VRT(geolocationArray=...) will be disabled in Nansat

INIT_LATLON_WARNING = u'VRT(lat=..., lon=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use VRT.

INIT_SRCMETADATA_WARNING = u'VRT(srcMetadata=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use V

INIT_VRTDATASET_WARNING = u'VRT(vrtDataset=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use VR

RAW_RASTER_BAND_SOURCE_XML = <string.Template object>

REPROJECT_TRANSFORMER = <string.Template object>

band_vrts = None

copy()

Create and return a full copy of a VRT instance with new filenames

If self.dataset has no bands, the copy is created also without bands. If self.dataset has bands, the copy is created from the dataset with all bands. If self has attribute 'vrt' (a sub-VRT object, result of get_super_vrt) it's contents is also copied into sub-VRT of the copy. Other attributes of self, such as tps flag and band_vrts are also copied.

classmethod copy_dataset (*gdal_dataset, **kwargs*)

Create VRT with bands and georeference as a full copy of input GDAL Dataset

Parameters

- **gdal_dataset** (*GDAL.Dataset*) – input dataset
- ****kwargs** (*dict*) – arguments for VRT()

Returns vrt

Return type *VRT*

copyproj (*filename*)

Copy geolocation data from given VRT to a figure file

Useful for adding geolocation information to figure files produced e.g. by Figure class, which contain no geolocation. Analogue to utility gdalcopyproj.py.

Parameters filename (*string*) – Name of file to which the geolocation data shall be written

create_band (*src, dst=None*)

Add band to self.dataset:

Get parameters of the source band(s) from input Generate source XML for the VRT, add options of creating Call GDALDataset.AddBand Set source and options Add metadata

Parameters

- **src** (*dict with parameters of sources:*) – SourceFilename SourceBand ScaleRatio ScaleOffset NODATA LUT SourceType DataType ImageOffset (RawVRT) PixelOffset (RawVRT) LineOffset (RawVRT) ByteOrder (RawVRT) xSize ySize
- **dst** (*dict with parameters of the created band*) – name dataType wk suffix AnyOtherMetadata PixelFunctionType: - band will be a pixel function defined by the

corresponding name/value. In this case src may be list of dicts with parameters for each source.

- in case the dst band has a different datatype than the source band it is important to add a SourceTransferType parameter in dst

SourceTransferType

Returns name

Return type string, name of the added band

Examples

```

vrt.create_band({'SourceFilename': filename, 'SourceBand': 1}) vrt.create_band({'SourceFilename':
filename, 'SourceBand': 2,
    'ScaleRatio': 0.0001},
    {'name': 'LAT', 'wkv': 'latitude'})

```

```

vrt.create_band({'SourceFilename': filename, 'SourceBand': 2},
    {'suffix': '670', 'wkv': 'brightness_temperature'})

```

```

vrt.create_band({'SourceFilename': filename, 'SourceBand': 1},
    {'SourceFilename': filename, 'SourceBand': 1}},
    {'PixelFunctionType': 'NameOfPixelFunction'})

```

create_bands (*metadata_dict*)

Generic function called from the mappers to create bands in the VRT dataset from an input dictionary of metadata

Parameters metadata_dict (*list of dict with params of input bands and generated bands.*)–

Each dict has: 'src' : dictionary with parameters of the sources: 'dst' : dictionary with parameters of the generated bands

Notes

Adds bands to the self.dataset based on info in metaDict

See also:

VRT.create_band()

create_geolocation_bands ()

Create bands from Geolocation

dataset = None

delete_band (*band_num*)

Delete a band from the given VRT

Parameters band_num (*int*) – band number

delete_bands (*band_nums*)

Delete bands

Parameters bandNums (*list*) – elements are int

driver = None

export (*filename*)

Export VRT file as XML into given <filename>

fileName

filename = u''

fix_band_metadata (*rm_metadata*)

Add NETCDF_VARNAME and remove <rm_metadata> in metadata for each band

fix_global_metadata (*rm_metadata*)

Remove unwanted global metadata and escape special characters

classmethod from_array (*array, **kwargs*)

Create VRT from numpy array with dataset with one band but without georeference.

Parameters

- **array** (*numpy.ndarray*) – array with data
- ****kwargs** (*dict*) – arguments for VRT()

Returns vrt

Return type *VRT*

classmethod from_dataset_params (*x_size, y_size, geo_transform, projection, gcps, gcp_projection, **kwargs*)

Create VRT from GDAL Dataset parameters

Create VRT with dataset without bands but with size/georeference corresponding to input parameters.

Parameters

- **x_size** (*int*) – X-size of dataset
- **y_size** (*int*) – Y-size of dataset
- **geotransform** (*tuple with 6 floats*) – information on affine transformation
- **projection** (*str*) – WKT representation of spatial reference system
- **gcps** (*tuple or list with GDAL GCP objects*) – GDAL Ground Control Points
- **gcp_projection** (*str*) – WKT representation of GCPs spatial reference system
- ****kwargs** (*dict*) – arguments for VRT()

Returns vrt

Return type *VRT*

classmethod from_gdal_dataset (*gdal_dataset, **kwargs*)

Create VRT from GDAL Dataset with the same size/georeference but without bands.

Parameters

- **gdal_dataset** (*gdal.Dataset*) – input GDAL dataset
- ****kwargs** (*dict*) – arguments for VRT()

Returns vrt

Return type *VRT*

classmethod from_lonlat (*lon, lat, **kwargs*)

Create VRT from longitude, latitude arrays

Create VRT with dataset without bands but with GEOLOCATION metadata and Geolocation object. Geolocation contains 2 2D arrays with lon/lat values given at regular pixel/line steps.

Parameters

- **lon** (*numpy.ndarray*) – array with longitudes
- **lat** (*numpy.ndarray*) – array with latitudes

- ****kwargs** (*dict*) – arguments for VRT()

Returns vrt

Return type *VRT*

get_projection()

Get projection from the dataset.

Uses `gdal.Dataset.GetProjection()` or `gdal.Dataset.GetGCPProjection()`. If both return an empty string, a `NansatProjectionError` is raised.

Returns projection

Return type projection or GCPprojection

Raises `NansatProjectionError` : occurs when the projection is empty.

get_resized_vrt (*x_size, y_size, resample_alg=1*)

Resize VRT

Create Warped VRT with modified `RasterXSize`, `RasterYSize`, `GeoTransform`. The returned VRT object has a copy of its original source VRT in its own vrt object (e.g. `warpedVRT.vrt = originalVRT.copy()`).

Parameters

- **y_size** (*x_size,*) – new size of the VRT object
- **resample_alg** (*GDALResampleAlg*) – see also `gdal.AutoCreateWarpedVRT`

Returns warped_vrt

Return type Resized VRT object

get_shifted_vrt (*shift_degree*)

Roll data in bands westwards or eastwards

Create `shift_vrt` which references `self`. Modify georeference of `shift_vrt` to account for the roll. Add as many bands as in `self` but for each band create two complex sources: for western and eastern parts. Keep `self` in `shift_vrt.vrt`

Parameters **shift_degree** (*float*) – rolling angle, how far east/west to roll

Returns shift_vrt

Return type VRT object with rolled bands

get_sub_vrt (*steps=1*)

Returns sub-VRT from given depth

Iteratively copy `self.vrt` into `self` until `self.vrt` is `None` or `steps == 0`

Parameters **steps** (*int*) – How many sub VRTs to restore

Returns

- **self** (*if no deeper VRTs found*)
- **self.vrt** (*if deeper VRTs are found*)

Notes

`self self.vrt`

get_subsampld_vrt (*new_raster_x_size, new_raster_y_size, resample_alg*)

Create VRT and replace step in the source

get_super_vrt ()

Create vrt with subVRT

copy of self in vrt.vrt and change references from vrt to vrt.vrt

get_warped_vrt (*dst_srs, x_size, y_size, geo_transform, resample_alg=0, dst_gcps=[], skip_gcps=1, block_size=None, working_data_type=None, resize_only=False*)

Create warped (reprojected) VRT object

1. Create a simple warped dataset using GDAL.AutoCreateWarpedVRT.
2. Create VRT from the warped dataset.
3. Modify the warped VRT according to the input options (size, geotransform, GCPs, etc)
4. Keep the original VRT in the attribute vrt

For reprojecting the function tries to use geolocation by default, if geolocation is not present it tries to use GCPs, if GCPs are not present it uses GeoTransform.

If destination image has GCPs (provided in <dst_gcps>): fake GCPs for referencing line/pixel of SRC image and X/Y of DST image are created and added to the SRC image. After warping the dst_gcps are added to the warped VRT.

Parameters

- **dst_srs** (*string*) – WKT of the destination projection
- **y_size** (*x_size,*) – dimensions of the destination raster
- **geo_transform** (*tuple with 6 floats*) – destination GDALGeoTransform
- **resample_alg** (*int (GDALResampleAlg)*) – 0 : NearestNeighbour, 1 : Bilinear, 2 : Cubic, 3 : CubicSpline, 4 : Lancos
- **dst_gcps** (*list with GDAL GCPs*) – GCPs of the destination image
- **skip_gcps** (*int*) – Using TPS can be very slow if the number of GCPs are large. If this parameter is given, only every [skip_gcp] GCP is used, improving calculation time at the cost of accuracy.
- **block_size** (*int*) – BlockSize to use for resampling. Larger blocksize reduces speed but increases accuracy.
- **working_data_type** (*str*) – ‘Float32’, ‘Int16’, etc.
- **resize_only** (*bool*) – Create warped_vrt which will be used for resizing only?

Returns warped_vrt

Return type VRT object with warped dataset and with vrt

hardcopy_bands ()

Make ‘hardcopy’ of bands: evaluate array from band and put into original band

leave_few_bands (*bands=None*)

Leave only given bands in VRT

logger = None**prepare_export_gtiff** (*options*)

Prepare dataset for export using GTiff driver

prepare_export_netcdf (*options, bottomup*)

Prepare dataset for export using netCDF driver

static read_vsi (*filename*)

Read text from input <filename:str> using VSI and return <content:str>.

reproject_GCPs (*dst_srs*)

Reproject all GCPs to a new spatial reference system

Necessary before warping an image if the given GCPs are in a coordinate system which has a singularity in (or near) the destination area (e.g. poles for lonlat GCPs)

Parameters *dst_srs* (*proj4*, *WKT*, *NSR*, *EPSG*) – Destination SRS given as any NSR input parameter

Notes

Reprojects all GCPs to new SRS and updates GCPProjection

set_offset_size (*axis*, *offset*, *size*)

Set offset and size in VRT dataset and band attributes

shift_cropped_gcps (*x_offset*, *x_size*, *y_offset*, *y_size*)

Modify GCPs to fit the size/offset of cropped image

shift_cropped_geo_transform (*x_offset*, *x_size*, *y_offset*, *y_size*)

Modify GeoTransform to fit the size/offset of the cropped image

split_complex_bands ()

Recursevely find complex bands and relace by real and imag components

tps = None

static transform_coordinates (*src_srs*, *src_points*, *dst_srs*)

Transform coordinates of points from one spatial reference to another

Parameters

- **src_srs** (*nansat.NSR*) – Source spatial reference system
- **src_points** (*tuple of two or three N-D arrays*) – Coordinates of points in the source spatial reference system. A tuple with (X, Y) or (X, Y, Z) coordinates arrays. Each coordinate Each array can be a list, 1D, 2D, N-D array.
- **dst_srs** (*nansat.NSR*) – Destination spatial reference

Returns *dst_points* – Coordinates of points in the destination spatial reference system. A tuple with (X, Y) or (X, Y, Z) coordinates arrays. Each coordinate Each array can be 1D, 2D, N-D array. Shape of output arrays corrrespond to shape of inputs.

Return type tuple of two or three N-D arrays

transform_points (*col_vector*, *row_vector*, *dst2src=0*, *dst_srs=<sphinx.ext.autodoc.importer._MockObject object>*, *dst_ds=None*, *options=None*)

Transform input pixel/line coordinates into lon/lat (or opposite)

Parameters

- **row_vector** (*col_vector*,) – X and Y coordinates with any coordinate system
- **dst2src** (*0 or 1*) – 1 for inverse transformation, 0 for forward transformation.
- **dst_srs** (*NSR*) – destination SRS.
- **dst_ds** (*GDAL Dataset*) – destination dataset. The default is None. It means transform ownPixLin <-> ownXY.

- **option** (*string*) – if ‘METHOD=GEOLOC_ARRAY’, specify here.

Returns `lon_vector`, `lat_vector` – X and Y coordinates in degree of lat/lon

Return type numpy arrays

`vrt = None`

write_xml (*vsi_file_content=None*)

Write XML content into a VRT dataset

Parameters `vsi_fileContent` (*string, optional*) – XML Content of the VSI file to write

Notes

self.dataset If XML content was written, `self.dataset` is re-opened

xml

Read XML content of the VRT-file using VSI

Returns `string`

Return type XML Content which is read from the VSI file

nansat.warnings module

exception `nansat.warnings.NansatFutureWarning`

Bases: `exceptions.Warning`

Module contents

`nansat.NSR`

Used by `autodoc_mock_imports`.

class `nansat.Domain` (*srs=None, ext=None, ds=None, lon=None, lat=None, name="", logLevel=None*)

Bases: `object`

Container for geographical reference of a raster

A Domain object describes all attributes of geographical reference of a raster:

- width and height (number of pixels)
- pixel size (e.g. in decimal degrees or in meters)
- relation between pixel/line coordinates and geographical coordinates (e.g. a linear relation)
- type of data projection (e.g. geographical or stereographic)

Parameters

- **srs** (*PROJ4 or EPSG or WKT or NSR or osr.SpatialReference()*) – Input parameter for `nansat.NSR()`
- **ext** (*string*) – some `gdalwarp` options + additional options [<http://www.gdal.org/gdalwarp.html>] Specifies extent, resolution / size Available options: (('te' or '-lle') and ('tr' or '-ts')) (e.g. '-lle -10 30 55 60 -ts 1000 1000' or '-te 100 2000 300 10000 -tr 300 200') -tr resolutionx resolutiony -ts sizex sizey -te xmin ymin xmax ymax -lle lonmin latmin lonmax latmax

- **ds** (*GDAL dataset*) –
- **lat** (*Numpy array*) – Grid with latitudes
- **lon** (*Numpy array*) – Grid with longitudes
- **name** (*string, optional*) – Name to be added to the Domain object
- **logLevel** (*int, optional*) – level of logging

Examples

```
>>> d = Domain(srs, ext) #size, extent and spatial reference is given by strings
>>> d = Domain(ds=GDALDataset) #size, extent copied from input GDAL dataset
>>> d = Domain(srs, ds=GDALDataset) # spatial reference is given by srs,
    but size and extent is determined from input GDAL dataset
>>> d = Domain(lon=lonGrid, lat=latGrid) # Size, extent and spatial reference is
↳given
    by two grids of longitude and latitude
```

Notes

The core of Domain is a GDAL Dataset. It has no bands, but only georeference information: rasterXsize, rasterYsize, GeoTransform and Projection or GCPs, etc. which fully describe dimensions and spatial reference of the grid.

There are three ways to store geo-reference in a GDAL dataset:

- Using GeoTransform to define linear relationship between raster pixel/line and geographical X/Y coordinates
- Using GCPs (set of Ground Control Points) to define non-linear relationship between pixel/line and X/Y
- Using Geolocation Array - full grids of X/Y coordinates for each pixel of a raster

The relation between X/Y coordinates of the raster and latitude/longitude coordinates is defined by projection type and projection parameters. These pieces of information are therefore stored in Domain:

- Type and parameters of projection + * GeoTransform, or * GCPs, or * GeolocationArrays

Domain has methods for basic operations with georeference information:

- creating georeference from input options;
- fetching corner, border or full grids of X/Y coordinates;
- making map of the georeferenced grid in a PNG or KML file;
- and some more...

The main attribute of Domain is a VRT object `self.vrt`. Nansat inherits from Domain and adds bands to `self.vrt`

Raises

- *NansatProjectionError* : occurs when `Projection()` is empty – despite it is required for creating `extentDic`.
- *OptionError* : occurs when the arguments are not proper.

See also:

Nansat.reproject() [<http://www.gdal.org/gdalwarp.html>] [<http://trac.osgeo.org/proj/>] [<http://spatialreference.org/>] [http://www.gdal.org/ogr/osr_tutorial.html]

KML_BASE = '<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>\n <kml xmlns="http://www.opengis.net'

OUTPUT_SEPARATOR = '-----\n'

REPROJECT_GCPs_WARNING = 'reproject_GCPs() will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use reproject'

WRITE_MAP_WARNING = 'Domain.write_map() will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use nansat.write'

azimuth_y (*reductionFactor=1*)

Calculate the angle of each pixel position vector with respect to the Y-axis (azimuth).

In general, azimuth is the angle from a reference vector (e.g., the direction to North) to the chosen position vector. The azimuth increases clockwise from direction to North. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Azimuth>

Parameters **reductionFactor** (*integer*) – factor by which the size of the output array is reduced

Returns **azimuth** – Values of azimuth in degrees in range 0 - 360

Return type numpy array

contains (*anotherDomain*)

Checks if this Domain fully covers another Domain

Returns **contains** – True if this Domain fully covers another Domain, False otherwise

Return type bool

get_border (*nPoints=10*)

Generate two vectors with values of lat/lon for the border of domain

Parameters **nPoints** (*int, optional*) – Number of points on each border

Returns **lonVec, latVec** – vectors with lon/lat values for each point at the border

Return type lists

get_border_geometry (**args, **kwargs*)

Get OGR Geometry of the border Polygon

Returns

Return type OGR Geometry, type Polygon

get_border_postgis ()

Get PostGIS formatted string of the border Polygon

Returns **str**

Return type 'PolygonFromText(PolygonWKT)'

get_border_wkt (**args, **kwargs*)

Creates string with WKT representation of the border polygon

Returns **WKTPolygon** – string with WKT representation of the border polygon

Return type string

get_corners ()

Get coordinates of corners of the Domain

Returns **lonVec, latVec** – vectors with lon/lat values for each corner

Return type lists

get_geolocation_grids (*stepSize=1, dstSRS=<sphinx.ext.autodoc.importer._MockObject object>*)

Get longitude and latitude grids representing the full data grid

If GEOLOCATION is not present in the self.vrt.dataset then grids are generated by converting pixel/line of each pixel into lat/lon If GEOLOCATION is present in the self.vrt.dataset then grids are read from the geolocation bands.

Parameters **stepSize** (*int*) – Reduction factor if output is desired on a reduced grid size

Returns

- **longitude** (*numpy array*) – grid with longitudes
- **latitude** (*numpy array*) – grid with latitudes

get_min_max_lon_lat ()

Get minimum and maximum of longitude and latitude geolocation grids

Returns **min_lon, max_lon, min_lat, max_lat**, – min/max lon/lat values for the Domain

Return type float

get_pixelsize_meters ()

Returns the pixelsize (deltaX, deltaY) of the domain

For projected domains, the exact result which is constant over the domain is returned. For geographic (lon-lat) projections, or domains with no geotransform, the haversine formula is used to calculate the pixel size in the center of the domain.

Returns **delta_x, delta_y** – pixel size in X and Y directions given in meters

Return type float

intersects (*anotherDomain*)

Checks if this Domain intersects another Domain

Returns **intersects** – True if Domains intersects, False otherwise

Return type bool

logger = None

name = None

overlaps (*anotherDomain*)

Checks if this Domain overlaps another Domain

Returns **overlaps** – True if Domains overlaps, False otherwise

Return type bool

reproject_GCPs (*srsString=""*)

reproject_gcps (*srs_string=""*)

Reproject all GCPs to a new spatial reference system

Necessary before warping an image if the given GCPs are in a coordinate system which has a singularity in (or near) the destination area (e.g. poles for lonlat GCPs)

Parameters **srs_string** (*string*) – SRS given as Proj4 string. If empty '+proj=stere' is used

Notes

Reprojects all GCPs to new SRS and updates GCPProjection

shape ()

Return Numpy-like shape of Domain object (ySize, xSize)

Returns **shape** – Numpy-like shape of Domain object (ySize, xSize)

Return type tuple of two INT

transform_points (*colVector*, *rowVector*, *DstToSrc=0*, *dstSRS=<sphinx.ext.autodoc.importer._MockObject object>*)

Transform given lists of X,Y coordinates into lon/lat or inverse

Parameters

- **colVector** (*lists*) – X and Y coordinates in pixel/line or lon/lat coordinate system
- **DstToSrc** (*0 or 1*) – 0 - forward transform (pix/line => lon/lat) 1 - inverse transformation
- **dstSRS** (*NSR*) – destination spatial reference

Returns **X, Y** – X and Y coordinates in lon/lat or pixel/line coordinate system

Return type lists

vrt = None

write_kml (*xmlFileName=None*, *kmlFileName=None*)

Write KML file with domains

Convert XML-file with domains into KML-file for GoogleEarth or write KML-file with the current Domain

Parameters

- **xmlFileName** (*string, optional*) – Name of the XML-file to convert. If only this value is given - `kmlFileName+xmlFileName+'.kml'`
- **kmlFileName** (*string, optional*) – Name of the KML-file to generate from the current Domain

write_kml_image (*kmlFileName*, *kmlFigureName=None*)

Create KML file for already projected image

Write Domain Image into KML-file for GoogleEarth

Parameters

- **kmlFileName** (*str*) – Name of the KML-file to generate from the current Domain
- **kmlFigureName** (*str*) – Name of the projected image stored in .png format

Examples

```
>>> n.undo(100) # cancel previous reprojection
>>> lons, lats = n.get_corners() # Get corners of the image and the pixel_
    ↳ resolution
>>> srsString = '+proj=latlong +datum=WGS84 +ellps=WGS84 +no_defs'
>>> extentString = '-l1e %f %f %f %f -ts 3000 3000'
```

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```

% (min(lon), min(lat), max(lon), max(lat))
>>> d = Domain(srs=srsString, ext=extentString) # Create Domain with
    stereographic projection, corner coordinates and resolution 1000m
>>> n.reproject(d)
>>> n.write_figure(filename=figureName, bands=[3], clim=[0,0.15],
    cmapName='gray', transparency=0)
>>> n.write_kml_image(kmlFileName=oPath + filename + '.kml',
    kmlFigureName=figureName) # 6.

```

write_map (*outputFileName*, *lonVec=None*, *latVec=None*, *lonBorder=10.0*, *latBorder=10.0*, *figureSize=(6, 6)*, *dpi=50*, *projection='cyl'*, *resolution='c'*, *continentsColor='coral'*, *meridians=10*, *parallels=10*, *pColor='r'*, *pLine='k'*, *pAlpha=0.5*, *padding=0.0*, *merLabels=[False, False, False, False]*, *parLabels=[False, False, False, False]*, *pltshow=False*, *labels=None*)

Create an image with a map of the domain

class `nansat.Nansat` (*filename=""*, *fileName=""*, *mapper=""*, *mapperName=""*, *domain=None*, *array=None*, *parameters=None*, *log_level=30*, *logLevel=None*, ***kwargs*)
 Bases: `nansat.domain.Domain`, `nansat.exporter.Exporter`

Container for geospatial data. Performs all high-level operations.

`n = Nansat(filename)` opens the file with satellite or model data for reading, adds scientific metadata to bands, and prepares the data for further handling.

Parameters

- **filename** (*str*) – uri of the input file or OpeNDAP datastream
- **mapper** (*str*) – name of the mapper from `nansat/mappers` dir. E.g. 'sentinel1_l1', 'asar', 'hirlam', 'meris_l1', 'meris_l2', etc.
- **log_level** (*int*) – Level of logging. See: <http://docs.python.org/howto/logging.html>
- **kwargs** (*additional arguments for mappers*) –

Examples

```

>>> n1 = Nansat(filename)
>>> n2 = Nansat(sentinel1_filename, mapper='sentinel1_l1')
>>> array1 = n1[1]
>>> array2 = n2['sigma0_HV']

```

Notes

The instance of `Nansat` class (the object `<n>`) contains information about geographical reference of the data (e.g raster size, pixel resolution, type of projection, etc) and about bands with values of geophysical variables (e.g. water leaving radiance, normalized radar cross section, chlorophyll concentration, etc). The object `<n>` has methods for high-level operations with data. E.g.: * reading data from file (`Nansat.__getitem__`); * visualization (`Nansat.write_figure`); * changing geographical reference (`Nansat.reproject`); * exporting (`Nansat.export`) * and much more...

`Nansat` inherits from `Domain` (container of geo-reference information) `Nansat` uses instance of `VRT` (wrapper around GDAL VRT-files) `Nansat` uses instance of `Figure` (collection of methods for visualization)

ALT_FILL_VALUE = -10000.0

FILL_VALUE = 9.96921e+36

INIT_BANDID_WARNING = 'Nansat.method(bandID=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use Nansat.f

INIT_DOMAIN_WARNING = 'Nansat(domain=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use Nansat.f

INIT_DSTDOMAIN_WARNING = 'Nansat.method(dstDomain=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1.

INIT_FILENAME_WARNING = 'Nansat(fileName=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use Nansat.f

INIT_GETBANDNUMBER_WARNING = 'Nansat._get_band_number() will be disabled in Nansat 1.1.

INIT_LOG_WARNING = 'Nansat(logLevel=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use Nansat(lo

INIT_MAPPER_WARNING = 'Nansat(mapperName=...) will be disabled in Nansat 1.1. Use Nansat

INIT_RESAMPLEALG_WARNING = 'Nansat.method(eResampleAlg=...) will be disabled in Nansat

add_band (*array*, *parameters=None*, *nomem=False*)

Add band from numpy array with metadata.

Create VRT object which contains VRT and RAW binary file and append it to self.vrt.band_vrts

Parameters

- **array** (*ndarray*) – new band data. Shape should be equal to shape
- **parameters** (*dict*) – band metadata: wkv, name, etc. (or for several bands)
- **nomem** (*bool*) – saves the vrt to a tempfile on disk?

Notes

Creates VRT object with VRT-file and RAW-file. Adds band to the self.vrt.

Examples

```
>>> n.add_band(array, {'name': 'new_data'}) # add new band and metadata, 
↳keep in memory
>>> n.add_band(array, nomem=True) # add new band, keep on disk
```

add_bands (*arrays*, *parameters=None*, *nomem=False*)

Add bands from numpy arrays with metadata.

Create VRT object which contains VRT and RAW binary file and append it to self.vrt.band_vrts

Parameters

- **arrays** (*list of ndarrays*) – new band data. Shape should be equal to shape
- **parameters** (*list of dict*) – band metadata: wkv, name, etc. (or for several bands)
- **nomem** (*bool*) – saves the vrt to a tempfile on disk?

Notes

Creates VRT object with VRT-file and RAW-file. Adds band to the self.vrt.

Examples

```
>>> n.add_bands([array1, array2]) # add new bands, keep in memory
```

bands ()

Make a dictionary with all metadata from all bands

Returns **b** – key = N, value = dict with all band metadata

Return type dictionary

crop (*x_offset, y_offset, x_size, y_size, allow_larger=False*)

Crop Nansat object

Create superVRT, modify the Source Rectangle (SrcRect) and Destination Rectangle (DstRect) tags in the VRT file for each band in order to take only part of the original image, create new GCPs or new GeoTransform for the cropped object.

Parameters

- **x_offset** (*int*) – pixel offset of subimage
- **y_offset** (*int*) – line offset of subimage
- **x_size** (*int*) – width in pixels of subimage
- **y_size** (*int*) – height in pixels of subimage
- **allow_larger** (*bool*) – Allow resulting extent to be larger than the original image?

Notes

self.vrt : super-VRT is created with modified SrcRect and DstRect

Returns **extent** – x_offset - X offset in the original dataset y_offset - Y offset in the original dataset x_size - width of the new dataset y_size - height of the new dataset

Return type (x_offset, y_offset, x_size, y_size)

Examples

```
>>> extent = n.crop(10, 20, 100, 200)
```

crop_interactive (*band=1, maxwidth=1000, **kwargs*)

Interactively select boundary and crop Nansat object

Parameters

- **band** (*int or str*) – id of the band to show for interactive selection of boundaries
- **maxwidth** (*int*) – large input data is downscaled to <maxwidth>
- ****kwargs** (*keyword arguments for imshow*) –

Notes

self.vrt [VRT] superVRT is created with modified SrcRect and DstRect

Returns extent – *x_offset* - X offset in the original dataset *y_offset* - Y offset in the original dataset *x_size* - width of the new dataset *y_size* - height of the new dataset

Return type (*x_offset*, *y_offset*, *x_size*, *y_size*)

Examples

```
>>> extent = n.crop_interactive(band=1) # crop a subimage interactively
```

crop_lonlat (*lonlim*, *latlim*)

Crop Nansat object to fit into given longitude/latitude limit

Parameters

- **lonlim** (*list of 2 float*) – min/max of longitude
- **latlim** (*list of 2 float*) – min/max of latitude

Notes

self.vrt [VRT] crops vrt to size that corresponds to lon/lat limits

Returns extent – *x_offset* - X offset in the original dataset *y_offset* - Y offset in the original dataset *x_size* - width of the new dataset *y_size* - height of the new dataset

Return type (*x_offset*, *y_offset*, *x_size*, *y_size*)

Examples

```
>>> extent = n.crop(lonlim=[-10,10], latlim=[-20,20]) # crop for given lon/
↳lat limits
```

digitize_points (*band=1*, ***kwargs*)

Get coordinates of interactively digitized points

Parameters

- **band** (*int or str*) – ID of Nansat band
- ****kwargs** (*keyword arguments for imshow*) –

Returns points – list of 2xN arrays of points to be used in `Nansat.get_transect()`

Return type list

extend (*left=0*, *right=0*, *top=0*, *bottom=0*)

Extend domain from four sides

Parameters

- **left** (*int*) – number of pixels to add from left side
- **right** (*int*) – number of pixels to add from right side

- **top** (*int*) – number of pixels to add from top side
- **bottom** (*int*) – number of pixels to add from bottom side

Notes

Changes self.vrt by adding nextgative offset or setting size to be large that original size.

fileName

filename = None

classmethod from_domain (*domain, array=None, parameters=None, log_level=30*)

Create Nansat object from input Domain [and array with data]

Parameters

- **domain** (*Domain*) – Defines spatial reference system and geographical extent.
- **array** (*numpy NDarray*) – Data for the first band. Shape must correspond to shape of <domain>
- **parameters** (*dict*) – Metadata for the first band. May contain ‘name’, ‘wkv’ and other keys.
- **log_level** (*int*) – Level of logging.

get_GDALRasterBand (*band_id=1, bandID=None*)

Get a GDALRasterBand of a given Nansat object

If str is given find corresponding band number If int is given check if band with this number exists. Get a GDALRasterBand from vrt.

Parameters band_id (*int or str*) – if int - a band number of the band to fetch if str
band_id = {‘name’: band_id}

Returns

Return type GDAL RasterBand

Example

```
>>> b = n.get_GDALRasterBand(1)
>>> b = n.get_GDALRasterBand('sigma0')
```

get_band_number (*band_id*)

Return absolute band number

Check if given band_id is valid Return absolute number of the band in the VRT

Parameters band_id (*int or str or dict*) – if int : checks if such band exists and returns band_id if str : finds band with coresponding name if dict : finds first band with given metadata

Returns int

Return type absolute band number

get_metadata (*key=None, band_id=None, bandID=None*)

Get metadata from self.vrt.dataset

Parameters

- **key** (*string, optional*) – name of the metadata key. If not given all metadata is returned
- **band_id** (*int or str, optional*) – number or name of band to get metadata from. If not given, global metadata is returned

Returns

- * *string with metadata if key is given and found*
- * *empty string if key is given and not found*
- * *dictionary with all metadata if key is not given*

get_transect (*points, bands, lonlat=True, smooth_radius=0, smooth_function=<sphinx.ext.autodoc.importer._MockObject object>, data=None, cornersonly=False*)

Get values from transect from given vector of points

Parameters

- **points** (*2xN list or array, N (number of points) >= 1*) – coordinates [[x1, x2, y2], [y1, y2, y3]]
- **bands** (*list of int or string*) – elements of the list are band number or band Name
- **lonlat** (*bool*) – If the points in lat/lon, then True. If the points in pixel/line, then False.
- **smooth_radius** (*int*) – If smoothRadius is greater than 0, smooth every transect pixel as the median or mean value in a circle with radius equal to the given number.
- **smooth_function** (*func*) – function for averaging values collected within smooth radius
- **data** (*ndarray*) – alternative array with data to take values from

Returns transect

Return type numpy record array

has_band (*band*)

Check if self has band with name <band> :param band: name or standard_name of the band to check
:type band: str

Returns

Return type True/False if band exists or not

list_bands (*do_print=True*)

Show band information of the given Nansat object

Show serial number, longName, name and all parameters for each band in the metadata of the given Nansat object.

Parameters do_print (*boolean*) – print on screen?

Returns outString – formatted string with bands info

Return type String

logger = None

mapper = None

name = None

path = None

reproject (*dst_domain=None, dstDomain=None, resample_alg=0, eResampleAlg=None, block_size=None, tps=None, skip_gcps=1, addmask=True, **kwargs*)

Change projection of the object based on the given Domain

Create superVRT from self.vrt with AutoCreateWarpedVRT() using projection from the dst_domain. Modify XML content of the warped vrt using the Domain parameters. Generate warpedVRT and replace self.vrt with warpedVRT. If current object spans from 0 to 360 and dst_domain is west of 0, the object is shifted by 180 westwards.

Parameters

- **dst_domain** (*domain*) – destination Domain where projection and resolution are set
- **resample_alg** (*int (GDALResampleAlg)*) – 0 : NearestNeighbour 1 : Bilinear 2 : Cubic, 3 : CubicSpline 4 : Lancos
- **block_size** (*int*) – size of blocks for resampling. Large value decrease speed but increase accuracy at the edge
- **tps** (*bool*) – Apply Thin Spline Transformation if source or destination has GCPs Usage of TPS can also be triggered by setting self.vrt.tps=True before calling to reproject. This options has priority over self.vrt.tps
- **skip_gcps** (*int*) – Using TPS can be very slow if the number of GCPs are large. If this parameter is given, only every [skip_gcp] GCP is used, improving calculation time at the cost of accuracy. If not given explicitly, ‘skip_gcps’ is fetched from the metadata of self, or from dst_domain (as set by mapper or user). [defaults to 1 if not specified, i.e. using all GCPs]
- **addmask** (*bool*) – If True, add band ‘swathmask’. 1 - valid data, 0 no-data. This band is used to replace no-data values with np.nan

Notes

self.vrt : VRT object with dataset replaced to warpedVRT dataset Integer data is returned by integer. Round off to decimal place. If you do not want to round off, convert the data types to GDT_Float32, GDT_Float64, or GDT_CFloat32.

See also:

http() //www.gdal.org/gdalwarp.html

resize (*factor=None, width=None, height=None, pixelsize=None, resample_alg=-1, eResampleAlg=None*)

Proportional resize of the dataset.

The dataset is resized as (x_size*factor, y_size*factor) If desired width, height or pixelsize is specified, the scaling factor is calculated accordingly. If GCPs are given in a dataset, they are also rewritten.

Parameters

- **factor** (*float, optional, default=1*) – Scaling factor for width and height > 1 means increasing domain size < 1 means decreasing domain size
- **width** (*int, optional*) – Desired new width in pixels
- **height** (*int, optional*) – Desired new height in pixels

- **pixelsize** (*float, optional*) – Desired new pixelsize in meters (approximate). A factor is calculated from ratio of the current pixelsize to the desired pixelsize.
- **resample_alg** (*int (GDALResampleAlg), optional*) –
-1 [Average (default),] **0** : NearestNeighbour **1** : Bilinear, **2** : Cubic, **3** : CubicSpline, **4** : Lancos

Notes

self.vrt.dataset [VRT dataset of VRT object] raster size are modified to downscaled size. If GCPs are given in the dataset, they are also overwritten.

set_metadata (*key="", value="", band_id=None, bandID=None*)
 Set metadata to self.vrt.dataset

Parameters

- **key** (*string or dictionary with strings*) – name of the metadata, or dictionary with metadata names, values
- **value** (*string*) – value of metadata
- **band_id** (*int or str*) – number or name of band Without : global metadata is set

Notes

self.vrt.dataset : sets metadata in GDAL current dataset

time_coverage_end

time_coverage_start

undo (*steps=1*)

Undo reproject, resize, add_band or crop of Nansat object

Restore the self.vrt from self.vrt.vrt

Parameters **steps** (*int*) – How many steps back to undo

Notes

Modifies self.vrt

vrt = None

watermask (*mod44path=None, dst_domain=None, dstDomain=None, **kwargs*)

Create numpy array with watermask (water=1, land=0)

250 meters resolution watermask from MODIS 44W Product: <http://www.glc.f.umd.edu/data/watermask/>

Watermask is stored as tiles in TIF(LZW) format and a VRT file All files are stored in one directory. A tarball with compressed TIF and VRT files should be additionally downloaded from the Nansat documentation page: <http://nansat.readthedocs.io/en/latest/source/features.html#differentiating-between-land-and-water>

The method : Gets the directory either from input parameter or from environment variable MOD44WPATH Open Nansat object from the VRT file Reprojects the watermask onto the current object using reproject() or reproject_on_jcps() Returns the reprojected Nansat object

Parameters

- **mod44path** (*string*) – path with MOD44W Products and a VRT file
- **dst_domain** (*Domain*) – destination domain other than self
- **tps** (*Bool*) – Use Thin Spline Transformation in reprojection of watermask? See also Nansat.reproject()
- **skip_gcps** (*int*) – Factor to reduce the number of GCPs by and increase speed See also Nansat.reproject()

Returns watermask

Return type Nansat object with water mask in current projection

See also:

http () //www.glc.f.umd.edu/data/watermask/

http () //nansat.readthedocs.io/en/latest/source/features.html#differentiating-between-land-and-water

write_figure (*filename=""*, *bands=1*, *clim=None*, *addDate=False*, *array_modfunc=None*, *file-Name=""*, ***kwargs*)

Save a raster band to a figure in graphical format.

Get numpy array from the band(s) and band information specified either by given band number or band id. – If three bands are given, merge them and create PIL image. – If one band is given, create indexed image Create Figure object and: Adjust the array brightness and contrast using the given min/max or histogram. Apply logarithmic scaling of color tone. Generate and append legend. Save the PIL output image in PNG or any other graphical format. If the filename extension is ‘tif’, the figure file is converted to GeoTiff

Parameters

- **filename** (*str*) – Output file name. if one of extensions ‘png’, ‘PNG’, ‘tif’, ‘TIF’, ‘bmp’, ‘BMP’, ‘jpg’, ‘JPG’, ‘jpeg’, ‘JPEG’ is included, specified file is created. otherwise, ‘png’ file is created.
- **bands** (*integer or string or list (elements are integer or string),*) – default = 1 the size of the list has to be 1 or 3. if the size is 3, RGB image is created based on the three bands. Then the first element is Red, the second is Green, and the third is Blue.
- **clim** (*list with two elements or 'hist' to specify range of colormap*) – None (default) : min/max values are fetched from WKV, fallback-‘hist’ [min, max] : min and max are numbers, or [[min, min, min], [max, max, max]]: three bands used ‘hist’ : a histogram is used to calculate min and max values
- **addDate** (*boolean*) – False (default) : no date will be added to the caption True : the first time of the object will be added to the caption
- **array_modfunc** (*None*) – None (default) : figure created using array in provided band function : figure created using array modified by provided function
- ****kwargs** (*parameters for Figure()*) –

Notes

if filename is specified, creates image file

Returns

Return type Figure object

Example

```
>>> n.write_figure('test.jpg') # write indexed image
>>> n.write_figure('test_rgb_hist.jpg', clim='hist', bands=[1, 2, 3]) # RGB_
↳image
>>> n.write_figure('r09_log3_leg.jpg', logarithm=True, legend=True,
                    gamma=3, titleString='Title', fontSize=30,
                    numOfTicks=15) # add legend
>>> n.write_figure(filename='transparent.png', bands=[3],
                    mask_array=wmArray,
                    mask_lut={0: [0,0,0]},
                    clim=[0,0.15], cmapName='gray',
                    transparency=[0,0,0]) # write transparent image
```

See also:

Figure()

http() //www.scipy.org/Cookbook/Matplotlib/Show_colormaps

write_geotiffimage (*filename, band_id=1, bandID=None*)

Writes an 8-bit GeoTiff image for a given band.

The colormap is fetched from the metadata item 'colormap'. Fallback colormap is 'gray'.

Color limits are fetched from the metadata item 'minmax'. If 'minmax' is not specified, min and max of the raster data is used.

The method can be replaced by using `nansat.write_figure()`. However, `write_figure` uses PIL, which does not allow Tiff compression. This gives much larger files.

Parameters

- **filename** (*str*) –
- **band_id** (*int or str*) –

class `nansat.Figure` (*narray, **kwargs*)

Bases: object

Perform operations with graphical files: create, append legend, save.

Figure instance is created in the `Nansat.write_figure` method. The methods below are applied consequently in order to generate a figure from one or three bands, estimate min/max, apply logarithmic scaling, convert to uint8, append legend, save to a file

CAPTION_LOCATION_X = 0.1

CAPTION_LOCATION_Y = 0.25

CBAR_HEIGHT = 0.15

CBAR_HEIGHTMIN = 5

CBAR_LOCATION_X = 0.1

```

CBAR_LOCATION_Y = 0.5
CBAR_WIDTH = 0.8
CBTICK_LOC_ADJUST_X = 5
CBTICK_LOC_ADJUST_Y = 3
DEFAULT_EXTENSION = '.png'
LEGEND_HEIGHT = 0.1
TITLE_LOCATION_X = 0.1
TITLE_LOCATION_Y = 0.05

```

add_latlon_grids (***kwargs*)

Add lat/lon grid lines into the PIL image

Compute step of the grid Make matrices with binarized lat/lon Find edge (make line) Convert to mask Add mask to PIL

Parameters

- of **Figure__init__()** **parameters** (*Any*) –
- **latGrid** (*numpy array*) – array with values of latitudes
- **lonGrid** (*numpy array*) – array with values of longitudes
- **lonTicks** (*int or list*) – number of lines to draw or locations of gridlines
- **latTicks** (*int or list*) – number of lines to draw or locations of gridlines
- **Modifies** –
- -----
- **self.pilImg** –

add_latlon_labels (***kwargs*)

Add lat/lon labels along upper and left side

Compute step of lables Get lat/lon for these labels from latGrid, lonGrid Print lables to PIL in white

Parameters

- of **Figure__init__()** **parameters** (*Any*) –
- **latGrid** (*numpy array*) – array with values of latitudes
- **lonGrid** (*numpy array*) – array with values of longitudes
- **lonTicks** (*int or list*) – number of lines to draw or locations of gridlines
- **latTicks** (*int or list*) – number of lines to draw or locations of gridlines
- **Modifies** –
- -----
- **self.pilImg** –

add_logo (***kwargs*)

Insert logo into the PIL image

Read logo from file as PIL Resize to the given size Pan using the given location Paste into pilImg

Parameters

- of `Figure.__init__()` parameters (Any) –
- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- `self.pilImg` –

apply_logarithm (**kwargs)

Apply a tone curve to the array

After the normalization of the values from 0 to 1, logarithm is applied Then the values are converted to the normal scale.

Parameters

- of `Figure.__init__()` parameters (Any) –
- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- `self.array` (numpy array) –

apply_mask (**kwargs)

Apply mask for coloring land, clouds, etc

If mask_array and mask_lut are provided as input parameters The pixels in self.array which have index equal to mask_lut key in mask_array will have color equal to mask_lut value

apply_mask should be called only after convert_palettesize (i.e. to uint8 data)

Parameters

- of `Figure.__init__()` parameters (Any) –
- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- `self.array` (numpy array) –

`array = None`

`caption = ''`

clim_from_histogram (**kwargs)

Estimate min and max pixel values from histogram

if ratio=1.0, simply the minimum and maximum values are returned. if $0 < \text{ratio} < 1.0$, get the histogram of the pixel values. Then get rid of $(1.0 - \text{ratio})/2$ from the both sides and return the minimum and maximum values.

Parameters of Figure.__init__() parameters (Any) –

Returns clim – minimum and maximum pixel values for each band

Return type numpy array 2D ((3x2) or (1x2))

clip (**kwargs)

Convert self.array to values between cmin and cmax

if pixel value $< \text{cmin}$, replaced to cmin. if pixel value $> \text{cmax}$, replaced to cmax.

Parameters

- of `Figure.__init__()` parameters (Any) –
- **Modifies** –

- -----
- **self.array** (*numpy array*) –
- **self.cmax** (*self.cmin,*) –

cmapName = 'jet'

cmax = [1.0]

cmin = [0.0]

convert_palettesize (***kwargs*)
Convert self.array to palette color size in uint8

Parameters

- of **Figure.__init__()** **parameters** (*Any*) –
- **Modifies** –
- -----
- **self.array** (*numpy array (=>uint8)*) –

create_legend (***kwargs*)
self.legend is replaced from None to PIL image
PIL image includes colorbar, caption, and titleString.

Parameters

- of **Figure.__init__()** **parameters** (*Any*) –
- **Modifies** –
- -----
- **self.legend** (*PIL image*) –

create_pilImage (***kwargs*)
self.create_pilImage is replaced from None to PIL image

If three images are given, create a image with RGB mode. if self.pilImgLegend is not None, it is pasted.

If one image is given, create a image with P(palette) mode. if self.pilImgLegend is not None, self.array is extended before create the pilImag and then paste pilImgLegend onto it.

Parameters

- of **Figure.__init__()** **parameters** (*Any*) –
- **Modifies** –
- -----
- **self.pilImg** (*PIL image*) – PIL image with / without the legend
- **self.array** (*replace to None*) –

extensionList = ['png', 'PNG', 'tif', 'TIF', 'bmp', 'BMP', 'jpg', 'JPG', 'jpeg', 'JPEG']

fontRatio = 1

fontSize = None

gamma = 2.0

```

latGrid = None
latTicks = 5
legend = False
logarithm = False
logoFileName = None
logoLocation = [0, 0]
logoSize = None
lonGrid = None
lonTicks = 5
mask_array = None
mask_lut = None
numOfColor = 250
numOfTicks = 5
palette = None
pilImg = None
pilImgLegend = None

```

process (**kwargs)

Do all common operations for preparation of a figure for saving

1. Modify default values of parameters by the provided ones (if any)
2. Clip to min/max
3. Apply logarithm if required
4. Convert data to uint8
5. Create palette
6. Apply mask for colouring land, clouds, etc if required
7. Create legend if required
8. Create PIL image
9. Add logo if required

Parameters

- of **Figure.__init__()** parameters (Any) –
- **Modifies** –
- ----- –
- **self.d** –
- **self.array** –
- **self.palette** –
- **self.pilImgLegend** –
- **self.pilImg** –

`ratio = 1.0`

`save (fileName, **kwargs)`

Save self.pilImg to a physical file

If given extension is JPG, convert the image mode from Palette to RGB

Parameters

- `fileName (string)` – name of outputfile
- of `Figure.__init__()` `parameters (Any)` –
- **Modifies** –
- -----
- `self.pilImg (None)` –

`subsetArraySize = 100000`

`titleString = ''`

`transparency = None`

3.2 nansat.mappers package

3.2.1 Submodules

3.2.2 nansat.mappers.envisat module

`class nansat.mappers.envisat.Envisat`

Bases: object

Methods/data shared between Envisat mappers

This class is needed to read awkward N1 format of ENVISAT Mostly it support reading of variables from ADS (additional data sets) which are TIE_POINTS_ADS (MERIS) or GEOLOCATION_GRID_ADS (ASAR)

`add_geolocation_from_ads (gdalDataset, zoomSize=500, step=1)`

Add geolocation domain metadata to the dataset

Get VRTs with zoomed arrays of lon and lat Create geolocation object and add to the metadata

Parameters

- `gdalDataset (GDAL Dataset)` – input dataset
- `zoomSize (int, optional, 500)` – size, to which the ADS array will be zoomed using scipy array of this size will be stored in memory
- `step (int)` – step of pixel and line in GeolocationArrays. lat/lon grids are generated at that step
- **Modifies** –
- -----
- **Geolocation Array metadata (Adds)** –

`allADSPParams = {'ASA_': {'width': 11, 'list': {'last_line longs': {'dataType': <sp`

create_VRT_from_ADS (*adsName*, *zoomSize=500*)

Create VRT with a band from Envisat ADS metadata

Read offsets of the <adsName> ADS. Read 2D matrix of binary values from ADS from file. Zoom array with ADS data to <zoomSize>. Zooming is needed to create smooth matrices. Array is zoomed to small size because it is stored in memory. Later the VRT with zoomed array is `VRT.get_resized_vrt()` in order to match the size of the Nansat object.

Create VRT from the ADS array.

Parameters

- **adsName** (*str*) – name of variable from ADS to read. should match allADSPParams
- **zoomSize** (*int, optional, 500*) – size, to which original matrix from ADSR is zoomed using `scipy.zoom`

Returns adsVrt

Return type *VRT*, vrt with a band created from ADS array

get_ads_vrts (*gdalDataset*, *adsNames*, *zoomSize=500*, *step=1*, ***kwargs*)

Create list with VRTs with zoomed and resized ADS arrays

For given names of variables (which should match self.allADSPParams): Get VRT with zoomed ADS array Get resized VRT

Parameters

- **gdalDataset** (*GDAL Dataset*) – input dataset
- **adsNames** (*list with strings*) – names of variables from `self.allADSPParams['list']`
- **zoomSize** (*int, 500*) – size to which the ADS array will be zoomed by `scipy.zoom`
- **step** (*int, 1*) – step, at which data will be given

Returns adsVRTs – list with resized VRT with zoomed arrays

Return type list with VRT

get_array_from_ADS (*adsName*)

Create VRT with a band from Envisat ADS metadata

Read offsets of the <adsName> ADS. Read 2D matrix of binary values from ADS from file. Read last line ADS (in case of ASAR). Zoom array with ADS data to <zoomSize>. Zooming is needed to create smooth matrices. Array is zoomed to small size because it is stored in memory. Later the VRT with zoomed array is `VRT.get_resized_vrt()` in order to match the size of the Nansat object. Create VRT from the ADS array.

Parameters adsName (*str*) – name of variable from ADS to read. should match allADSPParams

Returns adsVrt – vrt with a band created from ADS array

Return type *VRT*

lonlatNames = {'ASA_': ['first_line longs', 'first_line_lats'], 'MER_': ['longitude'

read_binary_line (*offset*, *fmtString*, *length*)

Read line with binary data at given offset

Open file Read values of given size, at given offset, given times Convert to list of values of given format and return

Parameters

- **offset** (*int*, *start of reading*) –
- **fmtString** (*str*, *data type format*) –
- **length** (*number of values to read*) –

Returns **binaryValues** – values which are read from the file. the number of elements is length

Return type list

read_offset_from_header (*gadsDSName*)

Read offset of ADS from text header.

Find a location of gadsDSName. Adjust the location with textOffset and read the text at the location. Convert the text to integer and set it into offsetDict.

Returns **offsetDict** – offset of DS, size of DS, number of records, size of record

Return type dictionary

read_scaling_gads (*indec*)

Read Scaling Factor GADS to get scalings of MERIS L1/L2

Parameters

- **filename** (*string*) –
- **indec** (*list*) –

Returns

Return type list

setup_ads_parameters (*filename*, *gdalMetadata*)

Select set of params and read offset of ADS

`structFmt = {<sphinx.ext.autodoc.importer._MockObject object at 0x7f03020dac50>: '>H'`

3.2.3 nansat.mappers.globcolour module

class `nansat.mappers.globcolour.Globcolour`

Mapper for GLOBCOLOR L3M products

make_rrsw_meta_entry (*nlwMetaEntry*)

Make metaEntry for calculation of Rrsw

`varname2wkv = {'BBP_mean': 'volume_backscattering_coefficient_of_radiative_flux_in_se`

3.2.4 nansat.mappers.hdf4_mapper module

class `nansat.mappers.hdf4_mapper.HDF4Mapper` (*x_size=1*, *y_size=1*, *metadata=None*, *nomem=False*, ***kwargs*)

Bases: `nansat.vrt.VRT`

find_metadata (*iMetadata*, *iKey*, *default=""*)

Find metadata which has similar key

Parameters

- **iMetadata** (*dict*) – input metadata, usually gdalMetadata
- **iKey** (*str*) – key to search for

- **default** (*str*) – default value

3.2.5 nansat.mappers.mapper_aapp_l1b module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_aapp_l1b.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata,
                                             **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

VRT with mapping of WKV for AVHRR L1B output from AAPP

3.2.6 nansat.mappers.mapper_aapp_l1c module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_aapp_l1c.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata,
                                             **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

VRT with mapping of WKV for AVHRR L1C output from AAPP

3.2.7 nansat.mappers.mapper_amsr2_l1r module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_amsr2_l1r.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMeta-
data, GCP_STEP=20, MAX_LAT=90,
                                             MIN_LAT=50, resolution='low',
                                             **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

Mapper for AMSR-2 L1 data

3.2.8 nansat.mappers.mapper_amsr2_l3 module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_amsr2_l3.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata,
                                             **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

Mapper for Level-3 AMSR2 data from <https://gcom-w1.jaxa.jp>

freqs = [6, 7, 10, 18, 23, 36, 89]

3.2.9 nansat.mappers.mapper_amsre_uham_leadfraction module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_amsre_uham_leadfraction.Mapper (filename, gdal-
Dataset, gdalMeta-
data, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

3.2.10 nansat.mappers.mapper_arome module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_arome.Mapper (*args, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.mappers.mapper_netcdf_cf.Mapper*

3.2.11 nansat.mappers.mapper_asar module

class nansat.mappers.mapper_asar.**Mapper** (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, **kwargs*)
Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT, nansat.mappers.envisat.Envisat*

VRT with mapping of WKV for ASAR Level 1

See also:

[http //envisat.esa.int/handbooks/asar/CNTR6-6-9.htm#eph.asar.asardf.asarrec.ASAR_Geo_Grid_ADSR](http://envisat.esa.int/handbooks/asar/CNTR6-6-9.htm#eph.asar.asardf.asarrec.ASAR_Geo_Grid_ADSR)

3.2.12 nansat.mappers.mapper_ascat_nasa module

class nansat.mappers.mapper_ascat_nasa.**Mapper** (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, lat-
lonGrid=None, mask="", **kwargs*)

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

Create VRT with mapping of WKV

3.2.13 nansat.mappers.mapper_aster_l1a module

class nansat.mappers.mapper_aster_l1a.**Mapper** (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMeta-
data, GCP_COUNT=10, band-
Names=['VNIR_Band1', 'VNIR_Band2',
'VNIR_Band3N'], bandWaves=[560, 660,
820], **kwargs*)

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

Mapper for ASTER L1A VNIR data

3.2.14 nansat.mappers.mapper_aster_l1b module

class nansat.mappers.mapper_aster_l1b.**Mapper** (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, em-
range='VNIR', **kwargs*)

Bases: *nansat.mappers.hdf4_mapper.HDF4Mapper*

VRT with mapping of WKV for MODIS Level 1 (QKM, HKM, 1KM)

3.2.15 nansat.mappers.mapper_case2reg module

class nansat.mappers.mapper_case2reg.**Mapper** (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, wave-
lengths=[None, 413, 443, 490, 510, 560,
620, 665, 681, 709, 753, None, 778, 864],
**kwargs*)

Bases: *nansat.mappers.mapper_generic.Mapper*

Mapping for the BEAM/Visat output of Case2Regional algorithm

3.2.16 nansat.mappers.mapper_cmems module

class nansat.mappers.mapper_cmems.**Mapper** (**args, **kwargs*)

Bases: *nansat.mappers.mapper_netcdf_cf.Mapper*

`time_coverage()`

`nansat.mappers.mapper_cmems.get_gcmd_keywords_mapping()`

3.2.17 nansat.mappers.mapper_csks module

class `nansat.mappers.mapper_csks.Mapper` (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, **kwargs*)

Bases: `nansat.vrt.VRT`

VRT with mapping of WKV for Cosmo-Skymed

3.2.18 nansat.mappers.mapper_ecmwf_metno module

class `nansat.mappers.mapper_ecmwf_metno.Mapper` (**args, **kwargs*)

Bases: `nansat.mappers.mapper_netcdf_cf.Mapper`

3.2.19 nansat.mappers.mapper_emodnet module

class `nansat.mappers.mapper_emodnet.Mapper` (*inputFileName, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, logLevel=30, **kwargs*)

Bases: `nansat.vrt.VRT`

3.2.20 nansat.mappers.mapper_generic module

class `nansat.mappers.mapper_generic.Mapper` (*inputFileName, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, logLevel=30, rmMetadata, datas=['NETCDF_VARNAME', '_Unsigned', 'ScaleRatio', 'ScaleOffset', 'dods_variable'], **kwargs*)

Bases: `nansat.vrt.VRT`

add_gcps_from_metadata (*geoMetadata*)

Get GCPs from strings in metadata and insert in dataset

add_gcps_from_variables (*filename*)

Get GCPs from GCPPixel, GCPLine, GCPX, GCPY, GCPZ variables

repare_projection (*projection*)

Replace odd symbols in projection string 'l' => ';' ; '&' => ''

3.2.21 nansat.mappers.mapper_globcolour_l3b module

class `nansat.mappers.mapper_globcolour_l3b.Mapper` (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, latlonGrid=None, mask="", **kwargs*)

Bases: `nansat.vrt.VRT, nansat.mappers.globcolour.Globcolour`

Create VRT with mapping of WKV for MERIS Level 2 (FR or RR)

3.2.22 nansat.mappers.mapper_globcolour_l3m module

class `nansat.mappers.mapper_globcolour_l3m.Mapper` (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, **kwargs*)

Bases: `nansat.vrt.VRT, nansat.mappers.globcolour.Globcolour`

Mapper for GLOBCOLOR L3M products

3.2.23 nansat.mappers.mapper_goci_l1 module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_goci_l1.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata,
                                             **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

VRT with mapping of WKV for MODIS Level 1 (QKM, HKM, 1KM)

3.2.24 nansat.mappers.mapper_hirlam module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_hirlam.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata,
                                             **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

VRT with mapping of WKV for HIRLAM

3.2.25 nansat.mappers.mapper_hirlam_wind_netcdf module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_hirlam_wind_netcdf.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdal-
                                                         Metadata, logLevel=30,
                                                         **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

3.2.26 nansat.mappers.mapper_kmss module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_kmss.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

VRT with mapping of WKV for KMSS TOA tiff data

3.2.27 nansat.mappers.mapper_landsat module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_landsat.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, resolu-
                                             tion='low', **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

Mapper for LANDSAT5,6,7,8 .tar.gz or tif files

3.2.28 nansat.mappers.mapper_meris_l1 module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_meris_l1.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, ge-
                                             olocation=False, zoomSize=500, step=1,
                                             **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*, *nansat.mappers.envisat.Envisat*

VRT with mapping of WKV for MERIS Level 1 (FR or RR)

3.2.29 nansat.mappers.mapper_meris_l2 module

class nansat.mappers.mapper_meris_l2.**Mapper** (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, geolocation=False, zoomSize=500, step=1, **kwargs*)

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT, nansat.mappers.envisat.Envisat*

Create VRT with mapping of WKV for MERIS Level 2 (FR or RR)

3.2.30 nansat.mappers.mapper_metno_hires_seaice module

class nansat.mappers.mapper_metno_hires_seaice.**Mapper** (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, **kwargs*)

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

Create VRT with mapping of WKV for Met.no seaice

3.2.31 nansat.mappers.mapper_metno_local_hires_seaice module

3.2.32 nansat.mappers.mapper_mod44w module

class nansat.mappers.mapper_mod44w.**Mapper** (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, **kwargs*)

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

VRT with mapping of WKV for MOD44W produc (MODIS watermark at 250 m)

3.2.33 nansat.mappers.mapper_modis_l1 module

class nansat.mappers.mapper_modis_l1.**Mapper** (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, GCP_COUNT=30, **kwargs*)

Bases: *nansat.mappers.hdf4_mapper.HDF4Mapper*

VRT with mapping of WKV for MODIS Level 1 (QKM, HKM, 1KM)

3.2.34 nansat.mappers.mapper_ncep module

class nansat.mappers.mapper_ncep.**Mapper** (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, **kwargs*)

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

VRT with mapping of WKV for NCEP GFS

3.2.35 nansat.mappers.mapper_ncep_wind module

class nansat.mappers.mapper_ncep_wind.**Mapper** (*filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, **kwargs*)

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

VRT with mapping of WKV for NCEP GFS

3.2.36 nansat.mappers.mapper_ncep_wind_online module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_ncep_wind_online.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset,
                                                    gdalMetadata, out-
                                                    Folder=u'/home/docs/ncep_gfs_downloads',
                                                    **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*, object

VRT with mapping of WKV for NCEP GFS

3.2.37 nansat.mappers.mapper_netcdf_cf module

Nansat NetCDF-CF mapper

Check CF-compliance of your files here: <http://cfconventions.org/compliance-checker.html>

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_netcdf_cf.Mapper (filename, gdal_dataset, gdal_metadata,
                                                    *args, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

times ()

Get times from time variable

NOTE: This cannot be done with gdal because the time variable is a vector

3.2.38 nansat.mappers.mapper_nora10_local_vpv module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_nora10_local_vpv.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdal-
                                                    Metadata, logLevel=30,
                                                    **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

3.2.39 nansat.mappers.mapper_obpg_l2 module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_obpg_l2.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata,
                                                    GCP_COUNT=10, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.mappers.obpg.OBPGL2BaseClass*

Mapper for SeaWIFS/MODIS/MERIS/VIIRS L2 data from OBPG

TODO: * Test on SeaWIFS * Test on MODIS Terra

3.2.40 nansat.mappers.mapper_obpg_l2_nc module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_obpg_l2_nc.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata,
                                                    GCP_COUNT=10, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.mappers.obpg.OBPGL2BaseClass*

Mapper for SeaWIFS/MODIS/MERIS/VIIRS L2 data from OBPG in NC4 format

3.2.41 nansat.mappers.mapper_obpg_l3 module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_obpg_l3.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata,
                                                    **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

Mapper for Level-3 Standard Mapped Image from <http://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov>

```
param2wkv = {'CDOM Index': u'volume_absorption_coefficient_of_radiative_flux_in_sea_...
```

3.2.42 nansat.mappers.mapper_ocean_productivity module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_ocean_productivity.Mapper(filename, gdalDataset, gdal-
    Metadata, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

Mapper for Ocean Productivity website <http://www.science.oregonstate.edu/ocean.productivity/>

```
bandNames = {'instantaneous_downwelling_photosynthetic_photon_radiance_in_sea_water':
```

```
param2wkv = {'bbp': 'particle_backscatter_at_443_nm', 'chl': 'mass_concentration_of_...
```

3.2.43 nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_arome module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_arome.Mapper(*args, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.mappers.opendap.Opendap*, *nansat.mappers.mapper_arome.Mapper*

```
baseURLs = ['http://thredds.met.no/thredds/catalog/arome25/catalog.html']
```

3.2.44 nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_globcurrent module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_globcurrent.Mapper(filename, gdalDataset,
    gdalMetadata, date=None,
    ds=None, bands=None,
    cachedir=None, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.mappers.opendap.Opendap*

VRT with mapping of WKV for NCEP GFS

```
baseURLs = ['http://www.ifremer.fr/opendap/cerdap1/globcurrent/v2.0/']
```

```
convert_dstime_datetimes(dsTime)
```

Convert time variable to np.datetime64

```
srcDSProjection
```

Used by autodoc_mock_imports.

```
timeCalendarStart = '1950-01-01'
```

```
timeVarName = 'time'
```

```
xName = 'lon'
```

```
yName = 'lat'
```

3.2.45 nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_globcurrent_thredds module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_globcurrent_thredds.Mapper (filename, gdal-  
Dataset, gdal-  
Metadata,  
date=None,  
ds=None,  
bands=None,  
cachedir=None,  
**kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.mappers.opendap.Opendap*

VRT with mapping of WKV for NCEP GFS

```
baseURLs = ['http://tds0.ifremer.fr/thredds/dodsC/CLS-L4']
```

```
convert_dstime_datetimes (dsTime)  
    Convert time variable to np.datetime64
```

```
srcDSProjection  
    Used by autodoc_mock_imports.
```

```
timeCalendarStart = '1950-01-01'
```

```
timeVarName = 'time'
```

```
xName = 'lon'
```

```
yName = 'lat'
```

3.2.46 nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_occci module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_occci.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata,  
date=None, ds=None, bands=None,  
cachedir=None, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.mappers.opendap.Opendap*

VRT with mapping of WKV for NCEP GFS

```
baseURLs = ['https://rsg.pml.ac.uk/thredds/dodsC/CCI_ALL', 'https://www.oceancolour.org']
```

```
convert_dstime_datetimes (dsTime)  
    Convert time variable to np.datetime64
```

```
srcDSProjection  
    Used by autodoc_mock_imports.
```

```
timeCalendarStart = '1970-01-01'
```

```
timeVarName = 'time'
```

```
xName = 'lon'
```

```
yName = 'lat'
```

3.2.47 nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_osisaf module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_osisaf.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdal-
Metadata, date=None, ds=None,
bands=None, cachedir=None,
**kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.mappers.opendap.Opendap*

VRT with mapping of WKV for NCEP GFS

```
baseURLs = ['http://thredds.met.no/thredds/dodsC/cryoclim/met.no/osisaf-nh', 'http://t/
```

```
convert_dstime_datetimes (dsTime)
    Convert time variable to np.datetime64
```

```
srcDSProjection
    Used by autodoc_mock_imports.
```

```
t0 = datetime.datetime(1978, 1, 1, 0, 0)
```

```
timeVarName = 'time'
```

```
xName = 'xc'
```

```
yName = 'yc'
```

3.2.48 nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_siwtacsst module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_siwtacsst.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdal-
Metadata, date=None, ds=None,
bands=None, cachedir=None, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.mappers.opendap.Opendap*

VRT with mapping of WKV for NCEP GFS

```
baseURLs = ['http://thredds.met.no/thredds/dodsC/myocean/siw-tac/sst-metno-arc-sst03/']
```

```
convert_dstime_datetimes (dsTime)
    Convert time variable to np.datetime64
```

```
srcDSProjection
    Used by autodoc_mock_imports.
```

```
t0 = datetime.datetime(1981, 1, 1, 0, 0)
```

```
timeVarName = 'time'
```

```
xName = 'lon'
```

```
yName = 'lat'
```

3.2.49 nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_sstcci module

```
class nansat.mappers.mapper_opendap_sstcci.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdal-
Metadata, date=None, ds=None,
bands=None, cachedir=None,
**kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.mappers.opendap.Opendap*

VRT with mapping of WKV for NCEP GFS

```

baseURLs = ['http://dap.ceda.ac.uk/data/neodc/esacci/sst/data/lt/Analysis/L4/v01.1/']
convert_dstime_datetimes (dsTime)
    Convert time variable to np.datetime64

srcDSProjection
    Used by autodoc_mock_imports.

timeCalendarStart = '1981-01-01'
timeVarName = 'time'
xName = 'lon'
yName = 'lat'

```

3.2.50 nansat.mappers.mapper_pathfinder52 module

```

class nansat.mappers.mapper_pathfinder52.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata,
                                                minQual=4, **kwargs)
    Bases: nansat.vrt.VRT
    Mapper PATHFINDER (local files)
    TODO: * remote files

```

3.2.51 nansat.mappers.mapper_radarsat2 module

```

class nansat.mappers.mapper_radarsat2.Mapper (inputFileName, gdalDataset, gdalMeta-
                                                data, xmlonly=False, **kwargs)
    Bases: nansat.vrt.VRT
    Create VRT with mapping of WKV for Radarsat2

init_from_xml (productXml)
    Fast init from metada in XML only

```

3.2.52 nansat.mappers.mapper_sentinel1_l1 module

```

class nansat.mappers.mapper_sentinel1_l1.Mapper (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata,
                                                fast=False, fixgcp=True, **kwargs)
    Bases: nansat.vrt.VRT

```

Create VRT with mapping of Sentinel-1 (A and B) stripmap mode (S1A_SM)

Parameters

- **filename** (*str*) – name of input Sentinel-1 L1 file
- **gdalDataset** (*None*) –
- **gdalMetadata** (*None*) –
- **fast** (*bool*) – Flag that triggers faster reading of metadata from Sentinel-1 file. If True, no bands are added to the dataset and georeference is not corrected. If False, all bands are added and GCPs are corrected if necessary (see Mapper.correct_geolocation_data for details).

Note: Creates self.dataset and populates it with S1 bands (when fast=False).

correct_geolocation_data ()

Correct lon/lat values in geolocation data for points high above ground (incorrect)

Each GCP in Sentinel-1 L1 image (both in the GeoTIF files and Annotation LUT) have five coordinates: X, Y, Z (height), Pixel and Line. On some scenes that cover Greenland (and probably other lands) some GCPs have height above zero even over ocean. This is incorrect, because the radar signal comes actually from the surface and not from a point above the ground as stipulated in such GCPs. Correction of GCPs in this function is equivalent to reverse DEM correction of SAR data.

Notes

Updates 'pixel' and 'height' in self.annotation_data

static create_gcps (x, y, z, p, l)

Create GCPs from geolocation data

Parameters

- **y, z, p, l** (*x*) –
- **arrays with value of X, Y, Z, Pixel and Line coordinates.** (*N-D*) –
- **and Y are typically lon, lat, Z - height.** (*X*) –

Returns gcps

Return type list with GDAL GCPs

read_annotation (annotation_files)

Read lon, lat, etc from annotation XML

Parameters: ———_ annotation_files : list
strings with names of annotation files

data [dict]

geolocation data from the XML as 2D np.arrays. Keys: pixel, line, longitude, latitude, height, incidenceAngle, elevationAngle: 2D arrays shape : tuple (shape of geolocation data arrays)
x_size, y_size : int pol : list

read_calibration (xml, vectorListName, variable_names, pol)

Read calibration data from calibration or noise XML files :param xml: String with XML from calibration or noise files :type xml: str :param vectorListName: tag of the element that contains lists with LUT values :type vectorListName: str :param variable_names: names of LUT variable to read :type variable_names: list of str :param pol: HH, HV, etc :type pol: str

Returns data – Calibration or noise data. Keys: The same as variable_names + 'pixel', 'line'

Return type dict

read_manifest_data (input_file)

Read information (time_coverage_start, etc) manifest XML

Parameters: ———_ input_file : str
name of manifest file

data [dict]

manifest data. Keys: `time_coverage_start` `time_coverage_end` `platform_familyName` `platform_number`

vrts_from_arrays (*data*, *variable_names*, *pol=""*, *resize=True*, *resample_alg=2*)
 Convert input dict with arrays into dict with VRTs

Parameters: _____ `_data` : dict

2D arrays with data from LUT

variable_names [list of str] variable names that should be converted to VRTs

pol [str] HH, HV, etc

resize [bool] Shall VRT be zoomed to full size?

resample_alg [int] Index of resampling algorithm. See `VRT.get_resized_vrt()`

`vrts` : dict with (resized) VRTs

3.2.53 nansat.mappers.mapper_sentinel1_l2 module

class `nansat.mappers.mapper_sentinel1_l2.Mapper` (*filename*, *gdalDataset*, *gdalMetadata*, *product_type='RVL'*, *GCP_COUNT=10*, ***kwargs*)

Bases: `nansat.vrt.VRT`

Create VRT with mapping of Sentinel-1A stripmap mode (S1A_SM)

3.2.54 nansat.mappers.mapper_topography module

class `nansat.mappers.mapper_topography.Mapper` (*filename*, *gdal_dataset*, **args*, ***kwargs*)

Bases: `nansat.vrt.VRT`

Mapping for the GTOPO30 (<https://lta.cr.usgs.gov/GTOPO30>) and the GMTED2010 (<https://lta.cr.usgs.gov/GMTED2010>) global elevation models.

filename [string] The vrt filename, e.g., `gtopo30.vrt`

gdal_dataset [osgeo.gdal.Dataset] The GDAL dataset returned by `gdal.Open(filename)`

Either the name of a GTOPO30 DEM file or GMTED2010 tif file, or `<path>/<dem>.vrt`. The latter is an aggregation of the DEM-files available from the given DEM. The GTOPO30 vrt does not contain the Antarctic, because this is in polarstereographic projection.

You can create your own `gtopo30.vrt` file with `gdal`, e.g.:

```
gdalbuildvrt <dem>.vrt [E,W]*.DEM
```

Remember to update this mapper by adding allowed filenames to the list of accepted filenames (`accepted_names`) if you create or apply new DEM datasets.

3.2.55 nansat.mappers.mapper_viirs_l1 module

class `nansat.mappers.mapper_viirs_l1.Mapper` (*filename*, *gdalDataset*, *gdalMetadata*, *GCP_COUNT0=5*, *GCP_COUNT1=20*, *pixelStep=1*, *lineStep=1*, ***kwargs*)

Bases: `nansat.vrt.VRT`

VRT with mapping of WKV for VIIRS Level 1B

3.2.56 nansat.mappers.obpg module

```
class nansat.mappers.obpg.OBPGL2BaseClass (x_size=1, y_size=1, metadata=None,
                                         nomem=False, **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

Base Class for Mappers for SeaWIFS/MODIS/MERIS/VIIRS L2 data from OBPG

```
titles = ['HMODISA Level-2 Data', 'MODISA Level-2 Data', 'HMODIST Level-2 Data', 'MERI
```

3.2.57 nansat.mappers.opendap module

```
class nansat.mappers.opendap.Opendap (x_size=1, y_size=1, metadata=None, nomem=False,
                                         **kwargs)
```

Bases: *nansat.vrt.VRT*

Methods for all OpenDAP mappers

```
P2S = {'D': 86400, 'H': 3600, 'M': 2592000, 'Y': 31536000}
```

```
create_vrt (filename, gdalDataset, gdalMetadata, date, ds, bands, cachedir)
    Create VRT
```

```
get_dataset (ds)
    Open Dataset
```

```
get_dataset_time ()
    Load data from time variable
```

```
get_geospatial_variable_names ()
    Get names of variables with both spatial dimentionions
```

```
get_geotransform ()
    Get first two values of X,Y variables and create geoTranform
```

```
get_layer_datetime (date, datetimes)
    Get datetime of the matching layer and layer number
```

```
get_metaitem (url, varName, layerNo)
    Set metadata for creating band VRT
```

```
get_shape ()
    Get srcRasterXSize and srcRasterYSize from OpenDAP
```

```
get_time_coverage_resolution ()
    Try to fetch time_coverage_resolution and convert to seconds
```

```
test_mapper (filename)
    Tests if filename fits mapper. May raise WrongMapperError
```

3.2.58 Module contents

CHAPTER 4

Please acknowledge Nansat

We appreciate acknowledgments of Nansat. If you use Nansat in scientific publications, please add a reference to the following paper:

Korosov A.A., Hansen M.W., Dagestad K.-F., Yamakawa A., Vines A., Riechert M., (2016). Nansat: a Scientist-Orientated Python Package for Geospatial Data Processing. *Journal of Open Research Software*. 4(1), p.e39. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5334/jors.120>

Differentiating between land and water

To add simple land- or water-masks to your figures, you can use the `watermask()` method in the main Nansat class. Download the prepared [MODIS 250M water-mask product](#) from our server and add the path to the directory with this data to an environment variable named `MOD44WPATH` (e.g. `MOD44WPATH=/Data/sat/auxdata/mod44w`).

Digital Elevation Models (DEMs)

6.1 Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data 2010 (GMTED2010)

The GMTED2010 datasets are provided by the U.S. Geological Survey. We have prepared a GDAL vrt file that can be used together with `mapper_topography.py` to open the 30 arcseconds Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with Nansat. To use it, the vrt file must be downloaded from ftp://ftp.nersc.no/nansat/dem/gmted2010_30.vrt and stored in the same folder as the tif files of *mean elevation* available at https://edcintl.cr.usgs.gov/downloads/sciweb1/shared/topo/downloads/GMTED/Global_tiles_GMTED/300darcsec/mean/.

In case you want to use a different DEM, the procedure is as follows:

1. Download the relevant GDAL readable files to a local folder
2. Generate a vrt file using `gdalbuildvrt`, e.g.:

```
gdalbuildvrt gmted2010_30.vrt *.tif
```

3. Update `mapper_topography.py` to accept the new kind of file(s)

6.2 Global 30 Arc-Second Elevation (GTOPO30)

We have also created a vrt-file for the GTOPO30 dataset. This is available as <ftp://ftp.nersc.no/nansat/dem/gtopo30.vrt>. The vrt-file should be placed in the same folder as the .DEM files available at https://dds.cr.usgs.gov/srtm/version2_1/SRTM30/.

7.1 Git branching and merging

We adopt the following system for branching and merging:

1. **master** branch: numbered releases of the code. Never edited. Merged from *develop* and *hot fix* branches (see notes on workflow below). Long living.
2. **develop** branch: rather stable version of code under development. Never edited. Merged from topic specific issue branches. Long living.
3. **issue<NNN>_<short-heading>** - issue specific branches (NNN = issue number). Main working area. Short living. Branched from, and merged back into develop.
4. **hotfix<NNN>_<short-heading>** - branches that are specific to a hotfix issue. Hotfixes are bugfixes on master that can not wait until next release.

Note:

1. Never edit code in the master or develop branch. Always make a new branch for your edits.
 2. A new branch should be very specific to only one problem. It should be short living.
 3. Commit often.
 4. Branch often.
 5. Branch only from master or from develop.
 6. Create pull requests for your branches and **always** assign a reviewer to merge, delete the branch, and close the issue (this is easy in github)
-

Example workflow for a hotfix (similar workflow for other branches):

1. Branch from master into the hotfix specific branch
 1. Update tests
-

2. Fix the bug
3. Increment micro version in `setup.py`
4. Commit to `hotfix<NNN>_<short-heading>`
2. Pull and merge master into your branch, test, and push
3. Go to <https://github.com/nanscenter/nansat> and add a pull request for the newly pushed branch and assign a reviewer
4. Let the reviewer do the following:
 1. Check the code
 2. Request changes or merge pull request into master
 3. Delete the branch
 4. Merge master into develop (again, use pull request, then merge by selecting the rebase option in GitHub)
5. Close the issue

Note: If you work on a project using Nansat, this project should use the master version of Nansat. Two situations may then occur:

1. You discover a **bug**. This can be solved with a **hotfix**.
 2. You want to add functionality to Nansat. This is solved by creating an issue in Nansat and a related issue branch. When this is completed and merged into develop, we may have a new release.
 3. You want to add a mapper. This can be done by adding a package `nansat_mappers` to your project. When the mapper is completed, create an issue and an issue-branch in Nansat, and finally submit a pull request with suggestion of a reviewer. You can still use the mapper via your `nansat_mappers` package until the new mapper is implemented in a release version of Nansat.
-

7.2 General conventions

- Nansat coding style generally follows [PEP-8 \(General style guide\)](#) and [PEP-257 \(Docstrings\)](#)
- Max line length is set to 100 chars
- Every unit of code must be properly tested (see `unit-test`) and documented
- All class/function/method/variable names have to be explicit and should contain no more than 3 words
- Single quotes should be used consistently instead of double quotes (except for cases where quotes are required, and for docstrings)
- GNU v3 licence should be inserted in all files. Mappers should have a standard header like this:

```
# Name:          mapper_asar.py
# Purpose:       Mapper for Envisat/ASAR data
# Authors:       Asuka Yamakava, Anton Korosov
# Licence:       This file is part of NANSAT. You can redistribute it or modify
#                under the terms of GNU General Public License, v.3
#                http://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.html
#
# Additional mapper/format specific links and information
```

- Docstrings should follow the [Numpy style](#)

- Available headers are ‘Parameters’, ‘Returns’, ‘Other parameters’, ‘Modifies’, ‘Crates’, ‘Raises’, ‘See also’, ‘Notes’, ‘References’ and ‘Examples’

7.2.1 Example function with complete Docstring

```
def some_function(start = 0, stop, step = 1):
    """ Return evenly spaced values within a given interval.

    | Values are generated within the half-open interval ''[start, stop)''
    | (in other words, the interval including 'start' but excluding 'stop').
    | For integer arguments the function is equivalent to the Python built-in
    | 'range' function, but returns a ndarray rather than a list.

    Parameters
    -----
    start : number, optional
        Start of interval. The interval includes this value. The default start_
↪value is 0.
    stop : number
        End of interval. The interval does not include this value.
    step : number, optional
        Spacing between values. For any output 'out', this is the distance between_
↪two adjacent values, 'out[i+1] - out[i]'. The default step size is 1. If 'step'_
↪is specified, 'start' must also be given.
    dtype : dtype
        The type of the output array. If 'dtype' is not given, infer the data type_
↪from the other input arguments.

    Returns
    -----
    out : ndarray
        Array of evenly spaced values.

        For floating point arguments, the length of the result is ''ceil((stop -_
↪start)/step)''. Because of floating point overflow, this rule may result in the_
↪last element of 'out' being greater than 'stop'.

    Modifies
    -----
    self.vrt : VRT
        Dataset RasterXSize and RasterYsaize are changed in the the current VRT_
↪dataset

    See Also
    -----
    linspace : Evenly spaced numbers with careful handling of endpoints
    ogrid: Arrays of evenly spaced numbers in N-dimensions
    mgrid: Grid-shaped arrays of evenly spaced numbers in N-dimensions

    Examples
    -----
    >>> np.arange(3)
    array([0, 1, 2])
    """
```

7.3 Naming conventions

- when a variable points to the GDALDataset, GDALDriver, etc. its name must always contain word “dataset”, “driver”, etc. representatively (raw_dataset, src_dataset, example_driver)
- when a variable points to a string with name it should contain ‘name’ (band_name)
- when longitude and latitude are input to (or output from) a function, they should be given in this order: (lon, lat). These variables should always be named ‘lon’ and ‘lat’ (i.e. never ‘long’).
- source and destination are prefixed as ‘src’ and ‘dst’ (src_dataset, dst_raster_xsize)
- band numbers should be called ‘band_number’
- GDAL bands should be called ‘band’ or, e.g., ‘dst_band’ when prefixed (GDAL is actually in-consistent here: gdal.Dataset.GetRasterBand returns a ‘Band’-object; hence ‘Band’ is the name of the class and the Python datatype)
- We use ‘filename’ (as in Python standard library)

7.4 Style checking

In your IDE/editor, it is highly recommended to activate/install a plugin for/script a save hook for doing automatic style checks and/or corrections, eg autopep8, pylint, pyflakes.

7.5 Tests

In general:

- Every function must be accompanied with a test suite
- Tests should be both positive (testing that the function work as intended with valid data) and negative (testing that the function behaves as expected with invalid data e.g. that correct exceptions are thrown)
- If a function has optional arguments, separate tests for all options should be created

7.5.1 Testing core Nansat functionality

- Tests for Nansat, Domain, etc should be added to nansat/tests/test_<module_name>.py file;
- These tests should be added as functions of classes inheriting from unittest.TestCase (e.g. DomainTest);
- Tests sharing similar set-up may inherit from the same class which has a setUp function;
- The core tests are run at [Travis CI](#) (continuous integration) which integrates with [Coveralls](#) for providing test coverage

7.5.2 Integration testing

Products read by Nansat mappers are tested in modules within the nansat_integration_tests folder in the repository root. These tests should have access to all the kinds of data read by nansat. Since this is a very large amount of data, and since we cannot share every data product openly, these tests are not presently executed at Travis CI. Every developer should add new end-to-end tests and execute them when new mappers or workflows are added. Unavailable

test data will lead to fewer tests being executed, i.e. they won't fail because of missing data. If possible, datasets used in new tests should be made available to the Nansen Center such that we can run the full test suite.

7.5.3 Testing mappers

General tests checking that the mappers don't violate the functionality of nansat and checks that some specific metadata is added, are collected in the `nansat_integration_tests.mapper_tests` module.

Also, we aim to create proper unit tests that use mock object for all the mappers. This will help to significantly increase the test coverage.

7.5.4 Testing specific data products or workflows

In typical scientific workflows, a data product is opened with Nansat and some operations are performed, e.g., adding new derived bands and exporting the results to a netcdf, or creating figures. To make sure that new versions of nansat do not harm these workflows with bugs or sudden interface changes, we collect tests for typical workflows in separate modules within the `nansat_integration_tests` package, e.g. `test_sar`, `test_radarsat2`, etc. We encourage users and developers to add such tests to avoid such potential problems

7.5.5 Doctests

TODO: add information about how to use doctests

About Nansat mappers

8.1 Concept

GDAL can read most satellite EO and NetCDF-CF compliant raster data relevant for Earth sciences. However, GDAL does not attach meaning to the contained information, i.e., it does not specify what kind of data is contained in a given band, e.g., if it is *water-leaving-radiance* used for monitoring of water quality. Nansat provides a mapping between geophysical variables of known meaning and the raster bands provided in the “Datasets” returned by GDAL.

The modules within the mappers package each contain a class defining the mapping between the bands returned from GDAL and metadata vocabularies provided via the `py-thesaurus-interface` package. For example, the simplest mapper for Meris level-1 data explicitly states that the first 15 bands are *upwelling_spectral_radiance* at 15 wavelengths and that the 16th band contains quality flags. The description of these bands require some compulsory metadata attributes to be defined in the mapper. These attributes follow certain given conventions:

- NetCDF-CF
- NASA GCMD keywords
- nersc-vocabularies

By using these conventions, the mappers thus attach unambiguous geophysical meaning to variables following the given standards. This allows the user to open and use a geo-referenced raster dataset with Nansat without depending on detailed apriori knowledge about the origin or type of the data.

8.2 Workflow

When we open a file with Nansat:

```
#!/usr/bin/env python
n = Nansat(filename)
```

these steps follow:

- The Nansat constructor calls `gdal.Open(filename)` to open the file with GDAL, and returns a GDAL Dataset with a list of available raster bands
- The Nansat constructor loops through available mappers and parses the Dataset to the mapper
 - Each mapper checks if the input Dataset is appropriate for the mapper, i.e., if the format, the metadata and the set of bands in the Dataset corresponds to what is expected in the mapper
 - * If the Dataset is not valid, the mapper silently fails and the next mapper is tested
 - * If the Dataset fits the mapper:
 - the mapper creates a [GDAL VRT file](#) with georeference and raster bands corresponding to the “well known variables” in [nersc-vocabularies](#) and adds respective metadata to each band (standard_name, units, etc).
- The mapper object, which is an instance of the VRT-class, is then returned to the Nansat instance as an attribute named `vrt` (`Nansat.vrt`)

The VRT has the following properties:

- we can use any available GDAL API functions, e.g., warping or exporting
- it contains georeferencing recognised by GDAL
- we can add PixelFunctions for, e.g., calculation of *speed* given two vector components of wind or current
- still it contains only Raster Bands with metadata which correspond to any of the NANSAT “Well Known Variables”

The Dataset may, e.g., be subsetted, reprojected, merged, etc., by simply modifying the VRT-file, either automatically by the GDAL high level applications/functions, or with NANSAT-specific Python logic. An important benefit of this approach is that we employ the *lazy processing concept* in GDAL.

Note: No processing or file reading/writing is performed before it is needed.

The VRT file defines a set of operations in xml format. When information is needed, data is extracted as numpy arrays for further processing or plotting. As such, we basically use the GDAL Datamodel and do not need to design our own.

8.3 Technical details

- The VRT-file is stored in memory using GDAL VSI-approach
- The VRT-class is a wrapper around the VRT-file. It has methods for generating, modifying, copying and other operations with VRT-files. VRT-class uses both GDAL methods and direct writing for modifying the VRT-file.
- Each mapper inherits the VRT-class.

8.4 Where to put new mappers?

If you have created a new mapper, you can either submit a pull request for inclusion in the nansat mappers package, or you can make a namespace package to let nansat discover your mapper automatically. This is done the following way:

1. Create a directory called *nansat_mappers* within a directory on your `$PYTHONPATH`
2. Inside *nansat_mappers*, create the file `__init__.py` with the following lines:

```
# __init__.py
from pkgutil import extend_path
__path__ = extend_path(__path__, __name__)
```

3. Add your mapper module (the filename should start with *mapper_* and end with *.py*) to the *nansat_mappers* folder
4. Reload your shell and start Python
5. Nansat should now find you mapper.

Note that user defined mappers have higher priority than standard mappers.

8.5 Required metadata added in the mappers

- TODO: add list of required metadata

8.6 Adding mapper tests

TODO: add documentation about how to write mapper tests

Releasing Nansat

9.1 General release procedure

In `setup.py`, Make sure the version is correct, by checking MAJOR, MINOR and MICRO, and that 'dev' is removed from VERSION.

Releases should be made from the master branch. **Make sure that Nansat works on all operating systems (Windows, Linux and OS X), with all combinations of python (py27, py35, py36) before releasing.**

When you are ready to release a new version, create a tag for the release and push it. The following creates a tag for version 0.6.17 and pushes it.

```
git tag "v0.6.17"  
git push origin --tags
```

Go to <https://github.com/nanscenter/nansat/releases> and click “Draft a new release”.

Select the tag version you just created, create a release title, for consistency, use the format of Nansat-0.6.17

Write some release notes that describes the changes done in this release.

9.2 Releasing on PiPy

Packaging documentation is found at [PyPA Packaging and Distributing Projects](#)

To avoid having to enter password when uploading, you can set `$HOME/.pypirc` as described in the above link.

```
conda create -n release_nansat -y python=3.6  
source activate release_nansat  
conda install -y -c conda-forge pythesint scipy=0.18.1 basemap netcdf4 gdal pillow  
pip install mock nose urllib3 twine  
python setup.py sdist  
# Check the dist file that was just created
```

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```
ls dist
# Should be a file on this format 'nansat-0.6.17.tar.gz'
twine upload dist/nansat-0.6.17.tar.gz
```

CHAPTER 10

Documenting Nansat

Documentation should follow the [conventions](#).

Note: Documentation for classes should be given after the class definition, not within the `__init__`-method.

To build documentation locally, the best is to create a virtual environment with the sphinx environment installed. This is done as follows:

```
cd docs
conda env create -n build_docs --file environment.yml
source activate build_docs
```

Then, the following commands should build the documentation:

```
make clean
sphinx-apidoc -fo source/ ../nansat
make html
```

Some documentation remains to be written. This is marked by `TODO` in the rst source files. Find open tasks by:

```
cd docs/source
grep TODO *
```


CHAPTER 11

Indices and tables

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